

Implementation of Industry 4.0 in Aerospace Manufacturing:
Operator 4.0 and Human-Centric Transformation

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In the name of Allah, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful.

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1 Abstract

The rapid advancement of Industry 4.0 (I4.0) has transformed global manufacturing, yet its adoption within aerospace remains fragmented due to complex regulations and workforce adaptation challenges. This dissertation critically examines these barriers and explores strategic solutions to accelerate I4.0 adoption. A comprehensive literature review establishes the conceptual foundations of I4.0, identifying key enabling technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Big Data Analytics (BDA). The study further investigates the emerging paradigm of Operator 4.0 (O4.0), emphasising its interplay with I4.0 and the evolving role of the workforce in cyber-physical manufacturing environments. Employing a meta-synthesis of qualitative case studies, this research extracts insights into O4.0 implementation in aerospace. A hybrid inductive-deductive reflexive thematic analysis identifies patterns, challenges, and strategic implications for I4.0-driven workforce transformation. Findings highlight the fragmented nature of O4.0 adoption, revealing that while productivity and quality improvements are prioritised, safety-focused digitalisation remains limited. Additionally, operator resistance to digital feedback mechanisms and the absence of key I4.0 technologies such as Virtual Reality (VR) suggest that technological feasibility alone does not guarantee adoption. This study contributes to the discourse on human-centric digital transformation in aerospace, offering industry leaders, policymakers, and researchers a structured foundation to navigate I4.0 adoption complexities. Future research should expand the dataset across multiple sectors, develop a taxonomy of O4.0 technologies, and investigate strategies to overcome cultural and psychological barriers to workforce engagement. Addressing these gaps paves the way for a more technologically advanced aerospace industry.

2 Introduction

2.1 Industry 4.0

The Fourth Industrial Revolution, more commonly known as Industry 4.0 (I4.0) originated in 2011 at the Hannover fair to mark a transformative era where digital, intelligent and interconnected technologies such as cloud computing, data analytics and autonomous robots are integrated into the industrial world (Carou, 2021; Ghobakhloo et al., 2022; Tabaković and Durakovic, 2021; Meindl et al., 2021). I4.0 has the potential to revolutionise production efficiency, enable predictive maintenance, and optimise supply chains (Gamal et al., 2024; Tabaković and Durakovic, 2021). By doing so, it empowers companies to develop smarter, more agile, and sustainable systems, driving economic growth and fostering innovation (Gamal et al., 2024).

In 2015, 88% of manufacturers were unfamiliar with the concept of I4.0 and its applications (WEF, 2015) and within just five years, 68% had made it a strategic priority (Yang and Gu, 2021). This is reflected in the volume of I4.0 literature. The author's search of the University of Warwick's (UoW) online library database of "Industr* 4.0" revealed 6,471 publications from 2013 to 2018. This number surged to 31,560 between 2019 and 2024, demonstrating a substantial shift in focus towards leveraging I4.0 in recent years.

The 'Lighthouse' Network which highlights leading manufacturers in I4.0 adoption, reveals that none of the 172 recognised companies are from the aerospace sector (WEF, 2024). Moreover, only 2% of publications in the last five years address the aerospace sector specifically, when searching UoW's database abstracts for "(Industr* 4.0) AND [(aero*) OR (aviation)]". This gap underscores the necessity for a tailored, industry-specific strategy to implement I4.0 technologies in aerospace, enabling the sector to capture and fully benefit from the potential value of I4.0.

2.2 Research Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of this dissertation is to explore the key barriers faced by aerospace manufacturers in adopting I4.0, and to propose a strategy that can be leveraged to navigate the complexities of I4.0. The following will be carried out:

- Evaluation of existing literature to gain a comprehensive understanding of I4.0, including the barriers to its adoption and the strategies that have been used to address these challenges.
- Formulation of research question/s to guide the study based on founded literature review.
- Design and implementation of an appropriate research methodology to collect insight data.
- Application of suitable statistical or qualitative methods for analysis of findings.
- Discussion of synthesised results, considering any limitations and future research directions.
- Conclusion to synthesise key findings from this research, evaluate the study's contributions, and outline actionable recommendations for the aerospace sector.

3 Literature Review

3.1 Industry 4.0 Overview

3.1.1 Concept

Many researchers have defined the concept of I4.0 in different ways (Table 1). Oztemel and Gursev (2020) emphasise the importance of understanding the features, content and I4.0 enabling technologies to understand its definition; they formulate a definition after analysing 619 publications. Gamal et al. (2024) describe I4.0 as a revolution that transcends industrial boundaries, reshaping not only manufacturing but also how we live, communicate, and interact with society. Hossain (2023) goes even further, stating that I4.0 enabling technologies, such as cloud computing and artificial intelligence, are intertwining not only with society, the economy, and culture but also with the human body and mind.

Source	Industry 4.0 Definition
Oztemel and Gursev (2020)	“Industry 4.0 is a manufacturing philosophy that includes modern automation systems with a certain level of autonomy, flexible and effective data exchanges encouraging the implementation of next-generation production technologies , innovation in design, and more personal and more agile production as well as customized products.”
Gamal et al. (2024)	“Industry 4.0 is characterized by the convergence of various innovative technologies , including artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things (IoT), blockchain, big data, and advanced robotics... a revolution that transcends industry boundaries, reshaping not only how we manufacture products but how we live, communicate, and interact with our surroundings ... not merely a discipline; it is a driving force shaping the world’s future.”
Hossain (2023)	“...recent technological advancements wherein the internet, along with supporting technologies and embedded systems , forms the foundation for integrating physical objects, human agents, intelligent machines, production lines, and processes across organizational boundaries.”

Table 1: Industry 4.0 Definitions from Literature (Gamal et al., 2024; Hossain, 2023; Oztemel and Gursev, 2020)

A common thread between these definitions is the mention of ‘enabling technologies’. Nosalska et al. (2020) state that when exploring the I4.0 concept and defining it, we should concentrate on the key trends that are transforming manufacturing and consumer markets. Culot et al. (2020) further provide a framework for navigating the concept in research, despite the absence of a universally accepted definition (Nosalska et al., 2020). The author has chosen to adopt this framework to navigate the complexities of I4.0 enabling a structured exploration of the concept:

- A context-specific approach is required as I4.0 is an umbrella concept for a broad range of technologies and applications
- Research needs to consider a multidisciplinary approach (beyond managerial disciplines) such as sociological, psychological and legal implications due to the vast reach and scope of I4.0.
- Academic investigations should be careful not to follow to the letter any closed list of key enabling technologies as the I4.0 landscape is still in a state of ‘flux’.

3.1.2 Nine Pillars of Industry 4.0

Scholars and practitioners commonly refer to the ‘9 Pillars of Industry 4.0’ as the core enabling technologies of I4.0 (Asadollahiyazdi et al., 2020; Aydın and Kahraman, 2022; Zutin et al., 2022). Originally articulated by the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) (Rüßmann et al., 2015), these pillars have been extensively adopted and referenced in academic literature. The 9 Pillars of I4.0 will serve as a foundation for this study, further developed using the framework proposed by Culot et al. (2020) to create a context-specific, industry-focused approach.

These pillars include Industrial Internet of Things (IIOT), System Integration, Additive Manufacturing (AM), Autonomous Robots, Cloud Computing, Big Data Analytics (BDA), Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR), Simulations and Cyber Security. Appendix A presents an overview of these pillars along with their definitions as described in scholarly works.

When examining pillars such as AM and Cloud Computing, specific details are emphasised in some sources while omitted in others. For instance, AM is often known for its ability to produce parts “on demand” (Bajic et al., 2021), while Cloud Computing is defined by its accessibility “at any time via the internet” (Aydın and Kahraman, 2022). Although the literature gathered to define these I4.0 pillars are tailored to the manufacturing industry following the recommendations of Nosalska et al. (2020), slight variations still exist across sources such as the omission of above details. These variations underscore the dynamic and evolving nature of I4.0, emphasising the need for a standardised yet flexible understanding of its pillars to facilitate effective implementation.

3.2 Industry 4.0 in Aerospace Manufacturing

The opportunities presented by I4.0 can allow aerospace manufacturers to stay competitive in the global market by producing goods more quickly, cost-effectively and with higher quality (Aydın and Kahraman, 2022). With the increased availability of these technologies, a focus on research and development to facilitate the seamless integration of intelligent processes is becoming more prominent (Zutin et al., 2022).

Several notable I4.0 initiatives are already underway at leading aerospace manufacturers such as Airbus, GE, and Lockheed Martin (Aydın and Kahraman, 2022; Bhatia et al., 2024; Carou, 2021). For example, AM has demonstrated impressive results, reducing component weights by up to 63% and increasing product lifespans by as much as five times (Carou, 2021). Boeing has implemented Big Data Analytics (BDA) to production data for predictive shimming, a process that estimates the geometry of shims before parts are assembled reducing the need for manual adjustments and ensuring a more precise fit of components (Bhatia et al., 2024).

However, a recent study revealed that only 17% of aerospace manufacturers have implemented I4.0 initiatives at scale, a figure that lags significantly behind I4.0 leaders in industries like automotive and healthcare (Marya, 2021) underscoring the need for strategic efforts to overcome the barriers and capitalise on I4.0’s transformative potential.

3.2.1 Industry 4.0 Enabling Technologies in Aerospace Manufacturing

Culot et al. (2020) argue that I4.0 research requires a context-specific lens rather than following a definitive list of I4.0 technologies. While this perspective aligns with the fluid and rapidly evolving nature of technological advancements, it also raises concerns regarding the fragmentation of research and the lack of a unified framework for assessing I4.0 implementation. The absence of a standardised classification risks inconsistency in both academic discourse and industrial practice, potentially hindering knowledge transfer and adoption across manufacturing sectors. To address this finding and the framework proposed by Culot et al. (2020), Table 2 presents a comparison between the Nine Pillars of I4.0 to five aerospace-focused sources, illustrating how I4.0 technologies intersect with industrial trends.

		Source							Sum
		Bhatia et al. (2024)	(Carou, 2021)	(Tabaković and Duraković, 2021)	Aydin and Kahraman (2022)	Zutin et al. (2022)	(Ghobakhloo et al., 2022)	(Bajic et al., 2021)	
Enabling I4.0 Technology	Industrial Internet of Things (IIOT)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	7
	Big Data and Analytics (BDA)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	7
	Cloud Computing	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	7
	Additive Manufacturing	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	7
	Autonomous Robots	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	7
	Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR)		X	X	X	X	X	X	6
	Simulations	X	X	X	X	X			5
	Cyber Security	X			X	X			3
	System Integration	X			X	X			3
	Artificial Intelligence	X	X	X			X		4
	Cyber Physical Systems	X					X	X	3
	Digital Twins	X	X						2
	Fog and Edge Computing	X						X	2
	Semantic Web							X	1
	Blockchain	X							1

Aerospace Specific Source
Pillar of Industry 4.0

Table 2: Comparison of I4.0 Enabling Technology Citation by Literature (Source: Author)

This comparison highlights a significant variation in the adoption of the core I4.0 pillars. Pillars, such as AM, BDA, and Cloud Computing, are frequently mentioned across multiple studies, reflecting their perceived centrality to I4.0 implementation. This consistency suggests that these technologies are not only well-established within the industry but also critical drivers of digital transformation in aerospace manufacturing.

In contrast, pillars like Cybersecurity and System Integration are mentioned less frequently, suggesting gaps in their prioritisation. This variation not only highlights differing priorities across aerospace but also raises critical questions about whether the focus on certain pillars is driven by their application or by a lack of awareness and adoption of the broader spectrum of I4.0 technologies.

Emerging technologies like Fog Computing and Blockchain appear sporadically suggesting either slow adoption or limited awareness in aerospace manufacturing. Given their transformative

potential by reducing data latency and enhancing supply chain security, respectively (Bajic et al., 2021; Bhatia et al., 2024), their under-representation could indicate a missed opportunity rather than irrelevance. Moreover, I4.0 technologies often function as interconnected clusters rather than discrete pillars. As Table 3 illustrates, Digital Twins and the Semantic Web, are frequently embedded within broader categories such as Simulations (Carou, 2021) and BDA (Bajic et al., 2021) respectively, highlighting inconsistencies in how technologies are classified and discussed. These inconsistencies suggest the need for a more unified framework that accommodates emerging technologies while ensuring a balanced focus on all pillars.

(Table 3) also reveals that the citation of enabling I4.0 technologies such as Cyber Security, Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) remain consistent across existing literature. In contrast, others such as IIoT and Cloud Computing often appear with their synonym terms and referenced through their technology subcategories, which serve as clusters that encapsulate related concepts. This variation underscores the inherent complexity and evolving nature of I4.0 terminology. The coexistence of overarching pillars and their associated subcategories within literature highlights the need for a standardised taxonomy, as agreed upon by current research (Culot et al., 2020; Meindl et al., 2021) to facilitate a more unified understanding of I4.0.

I4.0 Enabling Technology	Sub-terms
Industrial Internet of Things (IIOT)	IoT (Internet of Things) (Carou 2021, Zutin 2022, Ghobakhloo 2022, Bajic 2021)
Big Data and Analytics (BDA)	Text Analytics, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Data Mining, Predictive Modelling, Pattern Recognition, Network Analysis, Simulation, Semantic Web (Bhatia 2024)
Cloud Computing	Fog/Edge Computing (Bhatia 2024)
Additive Manufacturing (AM)	Stereolithography (SLA), Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM), Selective Laser Sintering (SLS), Selective Laser Melting (SLM), Electronic Beam Melting (EBM), PolyJet, Digital Light Processing (DLP), Laminated Object Manufacturing (LOM), Binder Jetting (Bhatia 2024)
Autonomous Robots	Articulated Robots, Humanoids, Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs), Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs), CoBots (Collaborative Robots) (Bhatia 2024)
Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR)	<i>(Stand Alone)</i>
Simulations	Agent-Based (Simulation), Monte Carlo (Simulation), Virtual Reality (Simulation) (Bhatia 2024, Carou 2021), Digital Twin (Bhatia 2024, Carou 2021)
Cyber Security	<i>(Stand Alone)</i>
System Integration	End-to-End Integration, Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) (Bhatia 2024)
Artificial Intelligence (AI)	Deep Multi-Layer Perceptron (DMLP), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) (Carou 2021)

Table 3: I4.0 Technologies and Associated Sub-terms in Literature (Source: Author)

Nosalska et al. (2020) highlight the use of ‘umbrella’ terms to describe a cluster or range of concepts. I4.0 enabling technologies that are outside the scope of the Nine I4.0 pillars are mentioned under these ‘umbrella’ terms from other sources (Table 4). These terms should be analysed as part of their ‘umbrella’ term to reduce ambiguity and allow for a clearer understanding of how each technology contributes to the I4.0 landscape (Culot et al., 2020). It also ensures more cohesive analysis by grouping related technologies, enhancing synergies between pillars and of-

fering a more holistic view of their collective impact on industrial transformation. Furthermore, it identifies opportunities to implement unified and scalable strategies to support the adoption of I4.0 (Culot et al., 2020).

I4.0 Enabling Technology	Umbrella
Artificial Intelligence	<i>(Stand Alone)</i>
Cyber Physical Systems	IIoT and CoBots (Bhatia et al., 2024; Carou, 2021)
Digital Twins	Simulations Cyber Physical Systems (Bhatia et al., 2024; Carou, 2021)
Fog and Edge Computing	Cloud Computing (Bhatia et al., 2024)
Semantic Web	BDA (Bhatia et al., 2024) Cyber-Physical Systems (Bajic et al., 2021)
Blockchain	Cyber Security (Bhatia et al., 2024)

Table 4: I4.0 Technologies and Associated Umbrella terms in Literature (Source: Author)

It is notable that Artificial Intelligence (AI), when cited, doesn't appear as part of a specific overarching category and has numerous sub-terms associated which are features of an I4.0 Pillars. Scholars argue that AI has a pervasive influence across multiple facets of I4.0, including BDA, IoT, and Cloud Computing, positioning it as a cross-functional enabler (Hossain, 2024; Carou, 2021) rather than a standalone pillar (Gabsi, 2024). Others (Hassan et al., 2024) agree, and argue that AI warrants recognition as a standalone pillar, particularly given its role in bridging I4.0 and emerging I5.0 paradigms. The exclusion of AI underscores the broader challenge of categorising evolving technologies within fixed taxonomies.

Although the Nine Pillars framework provides a foundational understanding, its rigidity may limit its ability to encompass evolving and cross-functional technologies like AI (Nosalska et al., 2020). Additionally, this rigidity potentially stifles innovation and fails to accommodate the dynamic progression of technological advancements. A more flexible taxonomy, accounting for both established and evolving technologies, would better reflect the dynamic nature of I4.0.

3.2.2 Industry 4.0 Prevalence and Trends

To assess the prevalence of I4.0 technologies in aerospace manufacturing, Bhatia et al., 2024 conducted a patent analysis (Appendix B) revealing that the number of I4.0 patents has almost doubled between 2019 and 2023. Robotics Industry's report estimated the robotics market at \$2.8 billion in 2020, with projections indicating it will reach \$8.1 billion by 2027 (Carou, 2021). With the rise of collaborative robots in recent years, research has increasingly focused on 'cobots' rather than traditional ones (Carou, 2021). As I4.0 pillars continue to evolve, emerging sub-technologies like cobots are becoming essential to defining and shaping the current I4.0 landscape.

AR and VR are frequently cited together as an I4.0 pillar in literature through real-time data visualisation and interactive maintenance support. Recent studies (Tabaković and Durakovic, 2021; Aydın and Kahraman, 2022; Zutin et al., 2022) show a nuanced approach with discussing AR as a critical tool without referencing VR. This selective focus suggests that AR has found greater immediate use in aerospace manufacturing than VR. J. Pirker (2022) investigates this further finding a decline in VR research in recent years and more niche uses outside the manufacturing realm such as in pilot training and telecommunications. This shift highlights how I4.0

pillars are continually refined, with technologies like AR gaining prominence over VR in specific sectors as their practical applications and value to industries like aerospace become clearer.

While the rapid growth of I4.0 technologies in aerospace manufacturing (Bhatia et al., 2024) underscores the sector's embrace of I4.0, it is important to consider the broader implications of these technological shifts. The rise of cobots and AR, along with the decline of VR in certain areas, suggests that while aerospace manufacturing is quick to adopt innovative technologies, it is also becoming more selective and strategic in its application. These trends raise significant questions about the scalability of I4.0 strategies across industries, given the nuanced and uneven adoption patterns observed in aerospace manufacturing.

3.3 Barriers and Enablers of Industry 4.0 Adoption

While I4.0 is becoming more popular in research and a higher business priority (Yang and Gu, 2021), several challenges such as digital illiteracy and limited financial resources force companies to either abandon digital transformation efforts or accept less impactful outcomes (Tabaković and Durakovic, 2021). In fact, only about 3% of digital transformation initiatives in the industry have been fully successful, with 29% failing outright and 69% yielding "suboptimal" results (Tabaković and Durakovic, 2021). This underscores the complexities surrounding I4.0 adoption and suggests an urgent need for targeted strategies to mitigate these barriers.

Literature (Bajic et al., 2021; Sharma et al., 2021) discusses the challenges of adopting Industry 4.0 (I4.0) technologies, categorising the obstacles into 'organisational,' 'technological,' and 'economic' factors. Guerrero, Mula, and Tormo (2023) go further by adding 'strategic' and 'sustainability' factors. Interestingly, most research has focused on the benefits of I4.0, often neglecting the systemic barriers that make its implementation difficult. To address this gap, Khan (2020) identifies Critical Success Factors (CSFs) to provide a more nuanced perspective.

Other studies (Guerrero, Mula, and Tormo, 2023; Ghobakhloo et al., 2022) advocate for a balanced approach that considers both challenges and success factors to develop effective strategies for implementation. This perspective aligns with the multidisciplinary framework proposed by Culot et al. (2020), emphasising the need for a holistic approach. Adopting this view can be critical to overcome the complexities of I4.0 adoption, ensuring that strategies are not only forward-looking but also consider surrounding factors that aid and hinder the implementation of I4.0.

3.3.1 Organisational Factors

Leadership

Leadership plays a pivotal role in shaping the success of I4.0 adoption. Strong executive commitment is a critical determinant (Bajic et al., 2021; Ghobakhloo et al., 2022; Guerrero, Mula, and Tormo, 2023; Khan, 2020). Pozzi et al. (2023) highlight that top management support, strategic clarity, and dedicated training initiatives are among the most frequently cited enablers of successful I4.0 implementation across all regions. Managerial shortcomings often result in failed digital initiatives (Ghobakhloo et al., 2022) emphasising the need for targeted leadership

development programmes.

To improve accountability and strategic focus, Guerrero, Mula, and Tormo (2023) suggest introducing leadership Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). This idea aligns with Sony and Naik (2022), who argue that managerial skills should be continuously refined through specialised training to ensure the successful execution of digital strategies. Interestingly, Bajic et al. (2021) note that leadership-related barriers are more significant in organisations at the early stages of I4.0 adoption, while more advanced adopters mainly face technological challenges. This indicates that a phased approach is needed, where leadership and strategic alignment are prioritised before addressing technical implementation issues.

Employee Involvement

Müller (2019) calls for an integrative approach that considers both managerial and employee perspectives, as workforce participation is crucial to successful implementation. Employee disengagement can act as a major barrier, particularly in applications requiring human-machine collaboration, such as collaborative robots (cobots) (Khan, 2020). The literature strongly supports the notion that continuous upskilling and reskilling are essential for ensuring workforce readiness in the era of I4.0 (Ghobakhloo et al., 2022; Pozzi et al., 2023).

However, the transition to I4.0 introduces significant challenges for employees, as traditional job roles evolve with the rise of Cyber-Physical Systems (Sony and Naik, 2020). This shift necessitates operators to adopt more advanced and cross-functional skill sets to navigate the complex and evolving nature of I4.0 systems (Sony and Naik, 2020).

The term ‘Operator 4.0’ (O4.0) conceptualises the future of digital and skilled workers considering the importance of building digital literacy and social aspects in operators to achieve high levels of I4.0 implementation (Marcon et al., 2022). This underscores the critical need for organisations to adopt a holistic approach that not only invests in advanced technologies but also prioritises the human and social dimension.

Cultural Resistance

Raj et al. (2020) explore the barriers to adopting I4.0 technologies in both developing and developed economies. They advise that developing economies should focus on overcoming internal capability and culture-related barriers more than developed ones. The work culture is a cornerstone for business decisions and must nurture innovation and motivation, which varies widely across different companies, industries, and countries (Raj et al., 2020; Khan, 2020).

This distinction highlights the need for strategies that are tailored to specific contexts, as the obstacles and facilitators for implementing I4.0 aren’t universally the same. Understanding these regional and cultural differences is essential for crafting an effective strategy that ensures the successful adoption of I4.0 technologies

Resource Availability

Ghobakhloo et al. (2022) note that small and medium enterprises (SMEs) face increased challenges in resource availability as they often lack the human resources of larger organisations,

putting them at a relative disadvantage in workforce readiness for I4.0.

Conversely, Marcon et al. (2021) observed that business size had no substantial impact on I4.0 adoption when comparing small Danish manufacturers to medium-sized counterparts. However, this finding may not necessarily extend to comparisons involving large enterprises, where differences in resources and capabilities could play a more pronounced role. This discrepancy highlights the need for further research to compare organisational challenges faced between SMEs and large enterprises.

Resource constraints extend beyond workforce readiness, with financial limitations presenting a significant barrier for SMEs in adopting I4.0 technologies (Bajic et al., 2021). Ghobakhloo et al. (2022) highlight that SMEs often face difficulties in securing the substantial capital investments needed for advanced technologies such as IoT, BDA, and robotics, placing them at a disadvantage compared to larger enterprises that can leverage economies of scale. To help bridge this gap, tailored support, such as subsidies and shared resources, is essential to help SMEs achieve effective I4.0 adoption (Ghobakhloo et al., 2022).

Even larger organisations encounter human resource challenges, not due to a lack of available capital, but because of resistance from management which can stem from uncertainty, a lack of strategic alignment, or cultural resistance (Bajic et al., 2021; Guerrero, Mula and Tormo, 2023). This highlights that the human and social barriers persist in organisations regardless of their size and strategies are relevant across organisational sizes.

3.3.2 Technological Factors

Technology Compatibility

If newly introduced systems are not able to replace all required requirements of current systems or lack the ability to communicate and exchange information with legacy systems, companies will be inclined toward unfavourable adoption (Ghobakhloo et al., 2022; Guerrero, Mula and Tormo, 2023; Khan, 2020).

Jayasekara et al. (2022) and Guerrero, Mula and Tormo (2023) identify limited compatibility with legacy systems as a significant challenge for aerospace manufacturers which leads to high costs in integration software as existing systems tend to be bespoke, one-off solutions. Jayasekara et al. (2022) further recommend that the software and devices should be ‘plug and play’ or ‘plug and produce’ to simplify integration and reduce reliance on external integrators. Initiatives such as OPC UA (Open Platform Communication Unified Architecture), ROSIN, and ROBIN, under the Horizon 2020 framework, aim to mitigate these challenges by developing standardised, interoperable solutions (Jayasekara et al., 2022).

Achieving seamless compatibility is also essential to prevent new technologies from creating bottlenecks in current processes (Bajic et al., 2021). This challenge is particularly evident with technologies that handle large datasets, such as BDA and Cloud Computing, where transitions can be technically complex, require additional back-end systems and are time-consuming to ensure data quality and integrity throughout (Guerrero, Mula and Tormo, 2023; Bajic et al.,

2021). These difficulties highlight the necessity for robust data management strategies to prevent new technologies from becoming bottlenecks rather than enablers of digital transformation.

In addition, achieving a high level of technological compatibility requires a comprehensive understanding of the technology configuration, the benefits associated, and the viable alternatives available (Khan, 2020; Guerrero, Mula and Tormo, 2023). Khan (2020) and Marcon et al. (2022) highlight several use cases where the I4.0 technology wasn't always an ideal or appropriate replacement. These findings underscore the critical need for organisations to conduct thorough feasibility assessments before embarking on I4.0 initiatives, ensuring alignment with operational requirements and long-term strategic objectives rather than merely following industry trends.

Data and Cybersecurity Concerns

BDA, Cloud Computing, and IoT rely on large datasets, which significantly increase the systems' vulnerability to unauthorised access, cyberattacks, data alterations, or destruction (Bajic et al., 2021; Khan, 2020). Sharma et al. (2021) regard this as the 'most complicated' aspect of introducing I4.0 to aerospace manufacturing due to the growing threat of cyber fraud; however, necessary safety measures introduce high expenditure on new Cyber Security technologies. To navigate this, many studies (Bajic et al., 2021; Khan, 2020; Sharma et al., 2021) emphasise the importance of establishing certified or accredited data policies during the early stages of implementation to safeguard data, personnel, and products (Khan, 2020).

Bajic et al. (2021) further note that data and cybersecurity concerns are particularly dominant in certain I4.0 technologies, such as BDA, Cloud Computing, and IoT, which currently dominate research efforts. In contrast, technologies like Robotics and AR/VR exhibit fewer cybersecurity challenges, as they remain less integrated into the I4.0 interconnected network. Bajic et al. (2021) comments that their limited visibility to I4.0 network designers and implementers suggests these technologies are still in the early stages of evolution. However, as the adoption and integration of these emerging technologies within I4.0 frameworks increase, their significance in cybersecurity research is expected to rise accordingly (Bajic et al., 2021; Sharma et al., 2021). This raises a critical gap in current research that many cybersecurity frameworks remain reactive rather than proactive and fail to anticipate future vulnerabilities as technologies evolve.

Additionally it introduces the paradox that while increased connectivity enhances efficiency and operational capabilities, it simultaneously increases exposure to cyber threats. This trade off suggests that manufacturers need to strike a balance between implementation of I4.0 and security resilience.

3.3.3 Strategic Factors

Researchers emphasise the importance of manufacturers establishing a clear I4.0-focused vision that aligns their goals and capabilities to prevent misalignment and underinvestment (Guerrero, Mula and Tormo, 2023; Khan, 2020; Marcon et al., 2022). Companies must commit to well-defined operational targets tied to the specific I4.0 technologies being implemented such as increasing productivity, shortening lead times, or reducing costs as each desired outcome necessitates a distinct I4.0 strategy to achieve higher levels of technological maturity (Marcon et al.,

2022).

An updated organisational vision should encompass all facets of the business, extending beyond production alone (Khan, 2020). Sony and Naik (2020) highlight the critical need for I4.0 in the supply chain to address the volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) nature of the industry. I4.0 technologies, such as IoT, BDA, and Cloud Computing enable extensive data acquisition, interpretation, and coordination capabilities that can empower aerospace manufacturers to respond effectively to rapidly changing customer demands, ultimately providing a significant competitive advantage (Bhatia et al., 2024; Carou, 2021; Sony and Naik, 2020).

Simply implementing these technologies does not guarantee performance improvements; rather, their effectiveness is contingent upon strategic alignment with business needs. This suggests that firms should adopt a more nuanced approach through balancing technological ambition with realistic assessments of capability and resource availability.

Implementation Methods

Manufacturers can adopt a phased or cellular approach to I4.0 implementation by focussing on pilot studies and selective stakeholder engagement (Khan, 2020). Sony and Naik (2020), in contrast advocate for a more radical transformation as they argue that I4.0 alters an organisation's deep structure through vertical, horizontal, and end-to-end integration. To fully realise its benefits, they emphasise that manufacturers must embrace a comprehensive and transformative approach to change. Ultimately, the choice of approach depends on the organisation's scale, strategic vision, and the anticipated value gained from the transformation (Marcon et al., 2022). This shows that companies must carefully evaluate their strategic priorities, balancing risk mitigation with the need for rapid digital transformation to remain competitive in an evolving industrial landscape.

3.3.4 Sustainability Factors

The growing focus on sustainability in manufacturing is driven by regulatory pressures, societal expectations, and corporate social responsibility (Sony and Naik, 2020). Despite its growing prominence, sustainability remains a vaguely defined concept, sparking ongoing debates about how to measure its effectiveness and justify investments (Franchino, 2023). While industry commitments such as the aerospace sector's goal of achieving net-zero emissions by 2050 set ambitious targets, the lack of clarity in sustainability assessment creates uncertainty about returns on investment (Dias et al., 2022). This raises questions about whether companies are prioritising sustainability for long-term impact or merely responding to external pressures without fully integrating it into their core strategy.

Environmental

With the global expansion of the aerospace industry, concerns over the environmental impact of airports, manufacturers, and airlines have grown significantly (Dias et al., 2022; Jayasekara et al., 2022). Tighter regulations on carbon emissions have pushed aerospace manufacturers to design more fuel-efficient aircraft and investigate alternative propulsion systems, including electric and hybrid engines (Pop and Titu, 2023).

However, despite the sector's commitment to achieving net-zero carbon emissions by 2050, many argue that current progress remains significantly off-track (Dias et al., 2022). This raises critical questions about the feasibility of existing sustainability roadmaps and whether they are ambitious yet unattainable.

The selection of I4.0 technologies plays a crucial role in advancing these environmental goals, yet the alignment between technology adoption and sustainability outcomes remains a significant challenge (Bajic et al., 2021; Franchino, 2023; Guerrero, Mula, and Tormo, 2023). Technologies like AM offer promising solutions by reducing material waste and enabling the production of lightweight, recyclable components (Bhatia et al., 2024; Carou, 2021). However, supply chain limitations, such as the small number of suppliers capable of developing these materials, hinder widespread adoption (Dias et al., 2022).

Moreover, while innovative materials receive considerable attention, waste management remains an overlooked area within the industry (Guerrero, Mula, and Tormo, 2023). This suggests a paradox: despite I4.0's potential to drive sustainability, its implementation often focuses on efficiency and cost-cutting rather than the broader environmental impact.

Regulatory

The strict quality and safety requirements in the aerospace industry tend to be barriers to the seamless implementation of I4.0 technologies (Pop and Titu, 2023; Guerrero, Mula and Tormo, 2023). Adhering to regulatory requirements is of utmost importance due to the critical nature and safety of the products and services offered so a process-based quality approach is essential to achieve the desired outcomes in alignment with the organisation's quality policy (Pop and Titu, 2023). Meeting these strict standards can slow down innovation, as companies may need to spend significant time and resources on compliance, delaying the adoption of new I4.0 technologies (Ghobakhloo et al., 2022; Pop and Titu, 2023). Finding a balance between ensuring quality and advancing technology is a key challenge for the industry.

Existing literature does not provide clear solutions for reconciling these competing demands. One possible approach is the introduction of regulatory sandboxes ie. controlled environments where new technologies can be tested under relaxed regulations before full-scale deployment. Despite their potential, such frameworks remain underexplored in aerospace manufacturing, representing a critical gap in regulatory research.

Social

A stronger emphasis on the social values and well-being of employees is likely to enhance the adoption of I4.0 technologies, as these advancements have the potential to create richer, more diverse roles with greater autonomy (Marcon et al., 2022). However, the transition can also pose risks to social and job security, potentially reducing employees' willingness to embrace change (Guerrero, Mula and Tormo, 2023; Sharma et al., 2021).

In socially mature systems, however, I4.0 technologies may be perceived positively, as they enable employees to shift away from simple or repetitive tasks toward more creative and higher-value-added activities, fostering a sense of human appreciation and professional growth (Marcon et

al., 2022). I4.0 technologies such as AI are deeply intertwined with social structures, and their implementation can inadvertently amplify class struggles if the technical and social aspects are not balanced (Sony and Naik, 2020). Hence, manufacturers need to consider the social implications to promote equitable growth and a more harmonious work environment.

3.4 Operator 4.0 and Industry 5.0

3.4.1 Operator 4.0: The Evolving Role of the Workforce

A recurring theme among the barriers and enablers of I4.0 adoption in aerospace manufacturing are of the social and human dimensions including the skills, knowledge, and abilities of people, particularly operators. The concept of Operator 4.0 (O4.0) seeks to bridge these gaps by fostering a trusting, interaction-based relationship between humans and technology (Zizic et al., 2022). The rise of O4.0 highlights the vital role of social sustainability in ensuring the successful adoption of the I4.0 paradigm.

Many argue that with the rise of technology, humans may become redundant in the next generation of manufacturing systems (Nujen et al., 2024). Romero, Stahre and Taisch (2020) challenge this by proposing a socially sustainable factory, also referred to as the ‘smart factory’ which adopts I4.0 technologies while fostering collaboration with human workers and machines as upheld by O4.0. To further illustrate this, Nujen et al. (2024) compile a typology consisting of eight distinct operator archetypes that highlight the reciprocal interaction between the human and technical elements of I4.0 (Appendix D).

However, the typology’s rationale has faced criticism for being rooted in the traditional assumption that machines inherently perform tasks better than humans, reflecting a techno-centric rather than a human-centric perspective, which contradicts the principles of O4.0 (Nujen et al., 2024). To align with O4.0’s vision, the allocation of tasks between I4.0 technologies and human workers must be carefully evaluated to ensure that operators are not relegated to the role of “second-class citizens” in the workplace (Romero, Stahre and Taisch, 2020; Zizic et al., 2022).

Another concern raised is that manufacturers find it difficult to focus on an O4.0 human-centric approach when introducing new technologies to the workforce, as it demands extreme skill (Kaasinen et al., 2020). In addition, Nujen et al. (2024) state that O4.0 is often analysed in isolation, despite the importance of social aspects for successful I4.0 implementation. The O4.0 typology integrates I4.0 enabling technologies to drive its success, emphasising the interconnected nature of these two topics. To facilitate the proper implementation of I4.0 into manufacturing, the human dimension must be prioritised through O4.0 (Kaasinen et al., 2020; Nujen et al., 2024; Romero, Stahre and Taisch, 2020; Zizic et al., 2022).

Moreover, manufacturers often face tension between adopting advanced technologies and maintaining a human-centric approach, as implementing O4.0 requires significant investment in workforce training and reskilling (Kaasinen et al., 2020). The tendency to analyse O4.0 in isolation further compounds this issue, as it neglects the broader social dimensions critical for the success of I4.0 initiatives (Nujen et al., 2024). This gap raises critical questions about whether current strategies truly support a human-centric digital transformation or whether they risk

marginalising the workforce through excessive automation. These challenges highlight the importance of balancing technological advancements with the social sustainability principles of O4.0 to ensure that operators remain integral contributors rather than passive participants in smart manufacturing systems.

3.4.2 Industry 5.0: The Human-Centric Evolution

When combined with the values of human-centricity and sustainability, I4.0 forms the foundation of the Fifth Industrial Revolution (5IR) or Industry 5.0 (I5.0) paradigm (Kaasinen et al., 2020). Although O4.0 is still in its early developmental stages, it plays a pivotal role as a bridge between I4.0 and I5.0 (Gladysz et al., 2023; Moenck et al., 2024, Zizic et al., 2022). Currently, aerospace manufacturers are not prioritising I5.0 due to lack of standardised strategies and research, especially regarding the human dimension (Moenck et al., 2024). As many I4.0 targets are still unmet, the industry stands at a crossroads, requiring a shift toward more inclusive and socially responsible manufacturing strategies.

Therefore, the critical question is how can O4.0 serve as a bridge between I4.0 and I5.0, facilitating a transition that prioritises human capabilities rather than displacing them.

4 Research Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology adopted to investigate the intersection of O4.0 and I4.0 in aerospace manufacturing. It describes the research purpose, methodological approach, and systematic steps taken to collect, analyse, and synthesise data.

4.1 Research Objectives and Questions

The research aim is to investigate the intersection of Operator 4.0 (O4.0) and Industry 4.0 (I4.0) within aerospace manufacturing to develop actionable strategies for overcoming the human dimension barriers. Specifically, the study seeks to identify the methods to drive O4.0, examine the intersection of O4.0 and I4.0, and evaluate the impact of addressing social aspects of O4.0 on I4.0 and influencing outcomes in aerospace manufacturing. To achieve these objectives, three research questions guide this study:

RQ1: Identify the methods used to drive Operator 4.0 in Aerospace Manufacturing.

RQ2: Examine the intersection between Operator 4.0 and Industry 4.0

RQ3: Evaluate the impact of addressing the social aspects of Operator 4.0 on Industry 4.0 in Aerospace Manufacturing.

4.2 Philosophical Assumptions and Theory Development

For the complex and ever-evolving phenomena of I4.0, Culot et al. (2020) recommend conducting 'intense exploratory' investigations, followed by organising and consolidating findings. Exploratory research is especially valuable for asking open-ended questions that uncover insights and deepen understanding of a topic (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019)

Moreover, Culot et al. (2020) suggest that, given the constantly changing nature of I4.0, research should not strictly adhere to any single theory from academic literature. Instead, they advocate for an inductive (or 'data-driven') approach that aligns with exploratory research and the philosophy of constructivism. This method focuses on deriving insights directly from the data itself, building theory from the ground up without any preconceived notions (Byrne, 2022). This allows for the discovery of new insights and patterns that are grounded in the data. Conversely, the deductive (or 'theory-driven') approach aligns with the philosophy of positivism and uses predefined theoretical frameworks to guide the analysis, providing a structured foundation for research (Byrne, 2022).

Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019) emphasise the importance of conducting analysis while referring back to existing literature and Culot et al. (2020) reiterate this in the context of I4.0 research. Equally, Byrne (2022) argues that it is impossible to perform an exclusively inductive analysis as the researcher requires criteria to identify whether a finding addresses the research question. Combining deductive and inductive analysis for I4.0 research ensures a comprehensive approach and allows the validation and refining of existing knowledge while remaining flexible to uncover new, context-specific insights (Culot et al., 2020).

This hybrid approach is particularly well-suited for tackling complex, evolving, and multidimensional topics such as the implementation of I4.0 in aerospace manufacturing. It ensures that the analysis captures both novel challenges and opportunities within specific industrial contexts (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006). In doing so, it supports a deeper, more holistic understanding of how I4.0 strategies are implemented in practice.

4.3 Methodical Choice

Many authors have conducted qualitative systematic literature reviews (SLR) when researching O4.0 (Nujen et al., 2024) and I4.0 (Bajic et al., 2021; Culot et al., 2020; Ghobakhloo et al., 2022; Hassan et al., 2024; Khan, 2020; Meindl et al., 2021; Nosalska et al., 2020; Sony and Naik, 2020; Timjerdine, Saoudi, and Moubachir, 2024). According to Meindl et al. (2021), SLRs are particularly effective in exploring the evolution, trends, and patterns of broad and complex topics like I4.0, providing a comprehensive understanding of their development and potential directions. They also synthesise existing knowledge, identify areas for future research, and address questions beyond the scope of individual studies (PRISMA, 2020; Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019).

Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019) stress the importance of having a clear research method. This clarity allows others to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the data reviewed. To achieve this, many researchers (Ghobakhloo et al., 2022; Khan, 2020; Nosalska et al., 2020; Timjerdine, Saoudi, and Moubachir, 2024; Zutin et al., 2022) use the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) checklist and flowchart. Initially developed for healthcare research, PRISMA has gained popularity in other fields and is widely endorsed in journals (PRISMA, 2020; Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019). This approach will be used to ensure the transparency and robustness of the qualitative research method.

4.4 Research Strategy

Eisenhardt and Graebner (2007) argue that insight from case studies are invaluable for theory development, bridging qualitative evidence and mainstream deductive research. Similarly, Hoon (2013) emphasises that synthesising qualitative case studies through an SLR offers significant insights into how organisations navigate change and implement strategies.

Case studies typically combine data collection methods such as archives, interviews, questionnaires, and observations (Eisenhardt, 1989). Hoon (2013) provides an eight-step research design for the meta-synthesis of qualitative case studies which is used by Nujen et al. (2024) to identify patterns, themes, and higher-order concepts across multiple O4.0 studies. In addition, Braun and Clarke regard thematic analysis as the ‘foundational method for qualitative analysis’ (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019) and their six-phase approach to reflexive thematic analysis has arguably become one of “the most thoroughly delineated” methods of conducting thematic analysis (Byrne, 2022).

By collating insights from multiple pre-published case studies, the research aims to construct a more unified understanding of I4.0 in aerospace manufacturing.

5 Data Collection

This chapter outlines the systematic and rigorous methodology employed to identify, select, and analyse relevant case studies for this research. Given the complex and interdisciplinary nature of O4.0 and its interplay with I4.0 in aerospace manufacturing, this chapter establishes a structured, phased approach (Table 5) to ensure the credibility, relevance, and depth of the data included in the study.

This follows the skeleton framework proposed by PRISMA (2020) but expanded on by methods detailed by Byrne (2022) and Hoon (2013) on the meta-synthesis of case studies. To ensure this framework’s robustness and that no phases are left out, each phase will be evaluated (Appendix E) in accordance with the SLR guidance from Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019).

Phase 1: Eligibility Criteria	(Hoon, 2013; PRISMA, 2020)
Phase 2: Search Strategy	(Hoon, 2013; PRISMA, 2020)
Phase 3: Selection Process	(PRISMA, 2020)
Phase 4: Data Extraction	(Byrne, 2022; Hoon, 2013; PRISMA, 2020)
Familiarisation	(Byrne, 2022)
Coding	(Byrne, 2022)
Case-Specific Level Analysis	(Hoon, 2013)
Phase 5: Data Synthesis	(Byrne, 2022; Hoon, 2013; PRISMA, 2020)
Generating Themes	(Byrne, 2022)
Reviewing Themes	(Byrne, 2022)
Cross-Study Analysis	(Hoon, 2013)
Defining and Naming Themes	(Byrne, 2022)

Table 5: Data Collection Framework Outline (Source: Author)

5.1 Phase 1: Eligibility Criteria

This study will include peer-reviewed journal articles, academic books, and reputable industry reports to ensure credibility and reliability. Literature must specifically address O4.0 and its interconnection with I4.0 in aerospace manufacturing. Closely related contexts, such as aircraft maintenance and defence manufacturing, are considered by the method of similarity. English-language sources are prioritised for consistency, with exceptions made for verified translations. To reflect the latest advancements, literature from the past five years is preferred, aligning with the growing prominence of O4.0, as evidenced by the author’s search and analysis (Appendix C), though foundational works are included for theoretical grounding.

Excluded sources include non-peer-reviewed articles, opinion pieces, gray literature, and blog posts to maintain research integrity. Purely theoretical studies lacking practical application and literature from unrelated sectors (e.g., healthcare, banking) are omitted due to misalignment with the research focus. Technologies outside the defined scope of I4.0 (Table 2, p.4) are excluded, as are sources providing insufficient detail on O4.0 implementation processes or outcomes, ensuring only relevant and impactful contributions are considered.

5.2 Phase 2: Search Strategy

5.2.1 Data Sources

Scopus and Web of Science will be used as per the recommendation of Hassan et al. (2024) to aggregate a comprehensive collection of scholarly contributions on the topic of O4.0. IEEE Xplore and ScienceDirect will be also used to access full-text articles from leading journals and a focused database on technological advancements literature.

5.2.2 Search Terms

The following keywords with Boolean operators will be used, inspired by the research designs of other authors investigating this subject (Gladysz et al., 2023; Kaasinen et al., 2020; Nujen et al., 2024; Romero, Stahre and Taisch, 2020):

- (“operator 4.0” OR ”smart operator”) AND (“aerospace” OR “aviation” OR “aeronautic”)
- (“operator 4.0” OR ”smart operator”) AND ”case stud*”

5.3 Phase 3: Study Selection Process

5.3.1 Screening Procedure

The study selection will follow the PRISMA (2020) flowchart and checklist (Appendix F) to include only relevant, high-quality studies. First, duplicates will be removed using Mendeley to ensure the same source isn’t reviewed multiple times. Next, titles and abstracts of the remaining studies will be screened against inclusion criteria. If uncertainty remains, the full text will be reviewed. Byrne (2022) and Hoon (2013) don’t specify an ideal number of case studies, but Eisenhardt (1989) suggests 4 to 10. Fewer than 4 may lead to unconvincing findings, while more than 10 can be overwhelming due to data complexity.

5.4 Phase 4: Data Extraction

To approach this phase, the author has drawn upon key techniques and principles from Bryne (2022), Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019), Eisenhardt and Graebner (2007), Eisenhardt (1989) and Hoon (2013).

5.4.1 Familiarisation

Byrne (2022) reveals that Braun and Clarke begin their six-phase framework first by ‘familiarisation of the data’. Immersing in the data better equips researchers to uncover hidden patterns, initial trends, and underlying themes, which are critical to answering the research questions (Eisenhardt, 1989; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Taking casual notes and re-reading literature actively refine the understanding of key themes to form early insights which can be developed in subsequent phases of the thematic framework (Byrne, 2022).

5.4.2 Coding

Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019) and Byrne (2022) emphasise that coding is a key component of thematic analysis, serving as the foundation for themes. Coding involves creating succinct, descriptive labels for information relevant to the research questions. Byrne (2022) highlights the importance of iterative refinements to ensure that codes accurately capture the essence of the data. Critical reflection is required to avoid superficial coding.

When working deductively, researchers may begin with a predefined codebook derived from relevant literature which ensures that the coding process remains grounded in existing knowledge and directly addresses the research questions (Byrne, 2022; Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019). The author will use keywords uncovered in the literature review (Table 2, 3, and 4) as the predefined codebook.

The deductive approach risks constraining the analysis to preconceived theoretical assumptions (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019), to mitigate this, the author remains open to inductive coding too, where new codes are generated from the data itself. This hybrid approach of balancing deductive and inductive processes not only enriches the analysis but also ensures flexibility and responsiveness to the evolving and unpredictable topic of I4.0 (Fereday and MuirCochrane, 2006; Byrne, 2022).

A predefined codebook provides a structured starting point but must not overshadow the unique contributions of the data (Hoon, 2013; Byrne, 2022). Rigid adherence to predefined codes can limit analysis depth (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019). Byrne (2022) suggests a recursive and reflective approach to coding, allowing for adaptation between deductive and inductive strategies as new insights emerge.

5.4.3 Case-Specific Level Analysis

Hoon (2013) in her framework for meta-synthesis of case studies recommends conducting a case-specific level analysis after refining the initial codes. This involves mapping each case on a ‘casual network’ which aids the researcher to understand how variables within a case connect to

build a coherent picture. By using causal networks, the author will visualise the relationships and interdependencies among variables, thereby uncovering deeper patterns that might remain hidden in traditional coding practices.

5.4.4 Data Extraction Tools

To ensure systematic and efficient data extraction, coding, and synthesis, the author will use NVivo, a qualitative data analysis software. Used by Khan (2020) for her SLR, NVivo enables researchers to manage large volumes of data, streamline the coding process, and organise extracted insights within a centralised platform (Lumivero, 2024). The software facilitates both deductive and inductive coding approaches, supporting the creation of predefined codebooks while remaining flexible to emerging themes and patterns identified during analysis. NVivo's capabilities, such as automated coding and visualisation tools allow for deeper exploration of relationships within the data and enhance transparency (Lumivero, 2024).

5.5 Phase 5: Data Synthesis

5.5.1 Generating Themes

Byrne (2022) highlights that after initial coding, the Braun and Clarke approach moves to interpreting patterns across the aggregated dataset. This involves grouping and refining codes to form themes and sub-themes. Codes sharing an underlying concept can be collapsed into a single theme, while others may fit better as part of a broader theme. Themes must be actively constructed, examined, and interpreted by the researcher.

Themes should be distinct yet may also be contradictory, reflecting the dataset's complexity. The researcher must remain flexible, refining the thematic framework by revising or removing codes or themes that don't contribute to the overall narrative or answer the research questions (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019; Byrne, 2022). Codes not aligning with any theme can be temporarily grouped under a miscellaneous category for re-evaluation later.

The number of themes is critical; too many can render the analysis fragmented, while too few may fail to capture the data's depth and diversity (Byrne, 2022). The author will follow the iterative and reflexive process to ensure that the themes are robust and meaningful, reflecting the dataset's complexities.

5.5.2 Reviewing Themes

Once initial themes are created, a recursive review process will be undertaken to refine and evaluate them. Braun and Clarke propose a set of key questions (Appendix G) to guide this review, such as whether the themes are distinct, coherent, and meaningful. Additionally, Byrne (2022) underscores the importance of Patton's dual criteria for judging categories, focusing on internal homogeneity and external heterogeneity.

By applying Braun and Clarke's guiding questions and Patton's dual criteria, the author ensures that the thematic framework is logically structured, with themes that are both internally coherent and externally diverse. This process is essential for enhancing the credibility, trustworthiness,

and analytical depth of the thematic analysis.

Patton's First Level of Review (Patton, 1990): Internal Homogeneity

At this stage, the author will examine the internal relationships between the codes that make up each theme or sub-theme. The goal is to assess whether these codes form a cohesive and logical pattern. Themes that lack internal homogeneity may appear unfocused or inconsistent, undermining their validity. This step often necessitates adjustments, such as merging or splitting themes, reassigning codes, or refining the definitions of sub-themes. This is done through creating concept maps on NVivo to visualise the internal relationships.

Patton's Second Level of Review (Patton, 1990): External Homogeneity

The second level shifts focus to how well the themes align with the entire dataset and address the overarching research questions. Here, the researcher evaluates whether the themes collectively provide a holistic and accurate interpretation of the data. Themes that are found to be redundant, irrelevant, or superficial can be removed or merged with others. Conversely, themes that fail to adequately represent the dataset may require additional codes, sub-themes, or re-definition to enhance their depth and scope. The author will group and rearrange themes on a cross-study concept map.

5.5.3 Defining and Naming Themes

This final stage consolidates the synthesis framework, where each theme is clearly defined and named in relation to the dataset and research questions. As per Patton (1990)'s criteria, each theme must offer an internally consistent and distinctive account of the data that cannot be subsumed by other themes. All themes must work together to tell a cohesive story that aligns with the dataset and provides meaningful insights into the research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019; Byrne, 2022). The author will highlight these themes on the final concept map.

5.6 Actual Data Collection

Using the initial boolean search, 184 sources were identified across 4 databases. This was then refined to 10 case studies using the inclusion and exclusion criteria. A summary of the selection process is represented by a PRISMA flowchart (Figure 1).

Figure 1: PRISMA Flowchart (Source: Author)

An initial familiarisation coding phase (Appendix H) was undertaken to ensure a comprehensive understanding of key themes and to form early insights into the data. Case-specific casual networks were compiled to further understand each source and internal homogeneity (Appendix I). Themes were generated using Patton’s first review (Appendix J) and Braun and Clarke’s prompts (Appendix G). A cross-study concept map was created to establish external homogeneity and visualise relationships across studies (Appendix K). A final concept map using Patton’s second review with named themes is established (Appendix L).

These findings are presented with reference to NVivo’s ‘concept maps’. To access the source data of themes, codes and subcodes found on the concept map and codebook, follow the steps listed in Appendix M. Following the research methodology outlined in previously, the author collected 184 sources, screened 120 and conducted a reflexive thematic analysis of 10 published Operator 4.0 case studies in Aerospace Manufacturing using NVivo 15. A summary of the published case studies used can be found in Appendix N.

6 Findings

6.1 Overview

The publication year of studies (2020-24) shows that the majority of case studies have been conducted in 2024 (50%) (Figure 2) further expressing the relevance of the topic. An analysis of the distribution of case study methodologies (Figure 3) revealed that the majority were conducted through in-person observations (60%) at manufacturing sites, while interviews (10%) and surveys (10%) were the least common methods employed. A quantitative review of the I4.0 technologies referenced highlights the prominence of AR (30%), followed by BDA (22%) and IoT (17%) (Figure 4). The companies included familiar industry players such as Baker Hughes, GKN Aerospace, and Boeing. However, limited information was available for the other 7 companies featured in the analysis, as these organisations chose to remain anonymous. Similarly, the

location of these case studies was not retrievable by the author.

Figure 2: Case Study Distribution by Year (Source: Author)

Figure 3: Case Study Type Distribution (Source: Author)

Figure 4: I4.0 Technology Distribution (Source: Author)

6.2 Contextual Findings

The thematic analysis of the context of the case studies revealed 3 core contextual themes: Aerospace Manufacturing Complexity in 6 cases Operator Demand in 4 cases and a Quality, Productivity and Safety focus across all.

Aerospace Manufacturing Complexity

This theme included part complexity, characterised by intricate geometries and strict dimensional tolerances; application complexity, reflected in the integration of numerous components working cohesively to form the end product; and process complexity, driven by the growing demand for customised products alongside low-volume production.

Operator Demand

Dangerous working conditions, coupled with diverse, complex, and manual processes, all with a strong emphasis on quality, place significant demands on operators to consistently meet high-performance standards. As a result, this theme reveals operators often face a stressful work environment, driven by the pressure to avoid defects, maintain safety and the need for specialised skills to navigate these complexities effectively.

Quality, Productivity and Safety Focus

The primary organisational focus across case studies revealed that most solutions aimed to enhance quality (40%) and productivity (40%), while only 20% prioritised safety (Figure 5). This distribution suggests a possible imbalance in how O4.0 initiatives address different operational goals, with safety receiving comparatively less emphasis.

Figure 5: Case Organisational Primary Focus (Source: Author)

	AI	AR	BDA	IoT	Sys' Int'	Cobot	Total
Productivity	0	3	2	1	1	0	7
Quality	2	3	2	1	1	1	10
Safety	1	1	1	2	0	1	6
Total	3	7	5	4	2	2	23

Table 6: Distribution of I4.0 Technologies Across Case Primary Focus (Source: Author)

The cases prioritising quality predominantly relied on AR (3 cases), BDA (2), and AI (2) (Table 6). AR was particularly effective in augmenting visual inspections, with two companies using it to overlay graphics onto components for geometric conformity assessment. This resulted in reduced defect rates and improved profitability.

Productivity-focused cases similarly leveraged AR (3 cases) and BDA (2), suggesting these technologies play a critical role in workflow efficiency and real-time data analysis. However, unlike quality-focused cases, AI was entirely absent from productivity applications, and cobots were not utilised at all. This absence raises questions about whether AI and cobots currently offer fewer direct benefits to productivity improvements or whether adoption barriers (e.g., cost, integration challenges) limit their implementation.

Safety was also identified as a key focus, particularly in improving ergonomics and mitigating challenges in hazardous working environments. The complete absence of system integration in safety-related cases suggests that safety measures may be implemented in isolation rather than as part of a broader, interconnected system.

6.3 Operator 4.0 and Industry 4.0

Each O4.0 case study integrated at least one I4.0-enabling technology identified in the literature review, with AR (30%) and BDA (22%) emerging as the most frequently utilised (Table 7). However, certain core I4.0 technologies such as Cloud Computing, AM, Simulation, VR, and

Cybersecurity—were entirely absent from the analysed cases, suggesting a minimal current role in enabling O4.0 applications. This omission raises questions about whether these technologies are inherently less relevant to O4.0, whether their benefits are not yet fully realised in this context, or whether organisational and technical barriers hinder adoption.

Additionally, several emerging technologies were identified inductively, including Visual Computing, Digital Work Instructions, and Model-Based Definition (MBD). These evolving tools indicate a broadening of the O4.0 and I4.0 landscape.

Case Name	AI	AR	BDA	Cobot	IoT	Sys' Int'	Total
Barbieri, L. et al. (2024)	0	1	0	0	0	1	2
Dimitropoulos, N. et al. (2024a)	1	0	1	1	1	0	4
Dimitropoulos, N. et al. (2024b)	1	0	1	1	0	0	3
Heikkilä, P. et al. (2021)	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Li, D. (2022)	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Petzoldt, C. et al. (2020)	1	1	1	1	0	0	4
Pinzone, M. et al. (2021)	0	1	1	0	1	1	4
Posada, J. (2021)	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Roberto, R. (2024a)	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Roberto, R. (2024b)	0	1	0	0	1	0	2
Total	3	7	5	2	4	2	23

Table 7: I4.0 Comparison by Case Study (Source: Author)

An analysis of technological correlations across the case studies (Table 7) suggests that certain I4.0 technologies are deployed in pairs suggesting a dependent relationship between technologies. For instance:

- AI and BDA frequently co-occur, reinforcing the notion that AI-driven analytics require a robust data infrastructure for effective implementation.
- Cobots and BDA appear in tandem, suggesting that collaborative robotics benefit from real-time data insights.
- IoT and BDA show a notable association, highlighting that sensor-generated data (IoT) is most valuable when processed and analysed through advanced data analytics (BDA).
- System Integration and AR are deployed together, likely due to AR's reliance on integrated data sources to deliver real-time, contextualised operator guidance.

These patterns imply that O4.0 implementations do not rely on single, isolated technologies but instead leverage interconnected systems. However, the limited sample size constrains the statistical robustness of these relationships, necessitating further investigation and validation.

Augmented Reality

AR emerged as a key technology in seven case studies, primarily for operator training, workload reduction, and hierarchical communication. While surveys and interviews reflected a general optimism about AR's usefulness, there was a divide in perceptions, with some operators embracing the technology and others resisting its adoption. Key challenges include:

- Specialised hardware and software requirements limiting accessibility.
- Environmental constraints, such as lighting conditions and surface reflections affecting inspection accuracy.
- Lack of customisation in off-the-shelf AR solutions posing barriers for companies with specialised needs.

Despite these obstacles, AR was found to facilitate system integration, improving horizontal and vertical communication across departments. Furthermore, AR's integration with Product Life-cycle Management (PLM) systems enhanced cross-team collaboration and knowledge sharing.

Cobots

Cobots were implemented to handle dangerous tasks, reduce ergonomic risks, and improve overall efficiency. In two cases, they led to ergonomic improvements, while three cases reported better overall safety.

In addition to their safety benefits, cobots demonstrated efficiency gains by reducing non-value-added (NVA) activities. Their integration with AI-driven decision making algorithms further optimised performance, enabling cobots to handle increasingly complex tasks. Operators were also found to play an active role in training cobots to manage a diverse range of parts allowing continuous improvements in precision and process quality.

Big Data Analytics

BDA played a pivotal role in four case studies in operator performance monitoring and feedback mechanisms. Data was collected from cobots, IoT sensors, and operator KPIs, providing insights into behaviour patterns such as posture and sleep habits. However, while awareness improved, it did not result to significant behavioural changes regarding sleep patterns.

Gamification was introduced in two cases, using elements such as badges, levels, and personalised avatars to motivate operators. Gamification fostered a sense of achievement, encouraging engagement and self-improvement. However, a key concern among operators was the potential misuse of performance data by management, leading to fears of increased surveillance and unfair comparisons. These fears contributes to a resistive environment and hinders the broader acceptance of I4.0 technologies.

6.4 Findings Conclusion

This section relates the author's findings to the research questions (RQ1, RQ2 and RQ3).

RQ1: Identify the methods used to drive Operator 4.0 in Aerospace Manufacturing.

- The most common method for investigating O4.0 in aerospace was in-person observations (60%), with interviews and surveys being less frequently used (10% each).
- Case studies demonstrated the use of Augmented Reality (AR) (30%), Big Data Analytics (BDA) (22%), and IoT (17%) as primary I4.0 technologies supporting O4.0 initiatives.

- Emerging technologies such as Visual Computing, Digital Work Instructions, and MBD were also identified as contributors to O4.0 applications.
- The primary drivers for O4.0 adoption were quality (40%), productivity (40%), and safety (20%), with safety receiving the least emphasis.
- Contextual themes including manufacturing complexity, operator demand, and organisational focus highlight the challenges and solutions shaping O4.0 adoption.

RQ2: Examine the intersection between Operator 4.0 and Industry 4.0

- All O4.0 cases leveraged at least one I4.0 technology, demonstrating a foundational reliance on I4.0.
- AI and BDA were consistently paired in O4.0 case studies, indicating an analytical dependency.
- AR and System Integration frequently co-occurred, suggesting that AR solutions benefit from integrated data sources.
- IoT and BDA showed a strong connection, indicating that IoT-generated data is most valuable when processed through analytics.
- IoT sensors, gamification, and data-driven feedback mechanisms further reinforce the connection between O4.0 and I4.0 systems by enabling data-driven decision-making and enhanced operator support.
- The absence of certain I4.0 technologies (e.g., Cloud Computing, Simulation) suggests selective applicability within O4.0 contexts.

RQ3: Evaluate the impact of addressing the social aspects of Operator 4.0 on Industry 4.0 in Aerospace Manufacturing.

- Gamification was used to engage operators, with elements such as badges and avatars improving motivation, though it did not significantly alter behavioural habits.
- Operator workload reduction, training, and hierarchical communication were key areas where AR was applied, but operator resistance to adoption was observed. AR also faced hardware and environmental limitations.
- Cobots enhanced operator safety and efficiency in hazardous environments.
- BDA increased behaviour awareness; however performance monitoring created tension as operators feared data misuse by management, leading to workplace surveillance concerns.

These Research Questions' (RQs) findings highlight that while O4.0 improves safety, productivity, and quality, its success depends on addressing human and social factors, ensuring transparency in data use, and fostering operator trust. Ignoring these human dimensions risks resistance, potentially undermining the broader adoption of I4.0 in aerospace manufacturing.

7 Discussion

7.1 Findings Discussion

This research identified Aerospace Manufacturing Complexity, Operator Demand, and a Focus on Quality, Productivity, and Safety as the key contextual themes influencing O4.0 and I4.0 implementation. However, a deeper critical examination reveals discrepancies and tensions between industry expectations and practical realities suggesting that O4.0 remains an evolving concept rather than a fully realised framework in aerospace manufacturing.

Complexity

The aerospace industry is documented as complex, with strict regulatory requirements, precision driven manufacturing, and high costs constraining adoption of new technology (Guyon et al., 2019; Pop & Titu, 2023). However, despite the industry’s inherent complexity, O4.0 implementations identified in this research were often simplistic, focusing on isolated solutions rather than fully integrated digital ecosystems. This raises concerns about whether O4.0 is being leveraged to its full potential or merely used as a superficial improvement to existing systems.

A comparative analysis with other high-complexity industries such as pharmaceuticals or automotive could illuminate whether the aerospace sector lags in its digital transformation or if its unique constraints necessitate a slower, more fragmented approach. Additionally, the limited research on scaling O4.0 solutions indicates that much of the focus remains on proof-of-concept stages. Future studies should emphasise longitudinal case analyses to explore how O4.0 initiatives develop beyond initial implementation.

Quality Focus

In these findings, quality emerged as a primary focus of O4.0 case studies. Current research argues that quality is of “paramount importance” and many manufacturers are adhering to Zero Defect standards set by regulatory bodies such as the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) and the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) (Pop and Titu, 2023; Guyon et al., 2019). However, contradictions emerge when comparing these findings with Robinson (2023)’s survey on organisational focus (Appendix O), where quality was not consistently prioritised.

This discrepancy suggests that while regulatory bodies enforce strict quality controls, operational realities may sometimes favour other factors such as cost and productivity over absolute quality. This highlights a potential gap between regulatory expectations and actual industry practices, warranting further investigation. Since only 27.32% of survey respondents were in management roles (Robinson, 2023), a follow-up survey targeting only those responsible for shaping company priorities would provide deeper insights.

Low Safety Focus

Despite safety being integral to aerospace manufacturing, it emerged as the lowest priority in O4.0 initiatives. This contradicts prior literature suggesting that O4.0 has the potential to enhance safety through real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and cobot integration (Nujen et al., 2024). This weak connection between safety and O4.0, implies that safety mea-

asures are often implemented independently of human-centric and I4.0 technologies. Rather than leveraging digital solutions through I4.0 for safety improvements, companies may still rely on traditional safety protocols.

One explanation for this could be that safety is perceived as a compliance issue rather than a driver of operational efficiency, leading to a lack of investment in digital safety methods. Alternatively, safety-related technologies may not yet be mature enough for seamless integration into O4.0 frameworks. Future research should investigate whether the exclusion of safety from digital transformation efforts is a strategic decision or an oversight. Additionally, conducting in-person observations at manufacturers can aid in verifying whether safety is genuinely deprioritised in O4.0 strategies or if it is addressed through alternative, less technology-driven means.

Operator Demand

This study's findings highlight the theme of a high demand for operator ability. Current research emphasises that reliance on manual processes in aerospace manufacturing remains significant, sustaining the demand for manual labour and skilled operators (Guyon et al., 2019). While O4.0 is often presented as a means to reduce operator workload, research (Pop and Titu, 2023) indicate that stress and human error remain persistent challenges, amplified by high expectations for precision and speed. Morandini et al. (2024) comment further that these factors, in turn, impact quality and safety in the manufacturing process.

This raises concerns about whether O4.0 is effectively addressing human factors or if its current implementation merely adds complexity without alleviating strain. If I4.0 technologies are increasing cognitive load rather than reducing it, they may be counterproductive. Conducting qualitative research through interviews and in-person observations on operator experiences, specifically focusing on stressors introduced by O4.0, could provide valuable insights into whether the technology is enhancing or hindering operator efficiency. Ensuring anonymity in these studies would allow participants to share their honest perspectives on workload, stress, and potential process inefficiencies without fear of exposing personal weaknesses or vulnerabilities.

Productivity

O4.0 has been found to drive productivity gains. However, key technologies expected to boost productivity, like cobots and AI, were notably missing in the case studies. This contrasts with earlier research (Pérez et al., 2020; Bhatia et al., 2024) that suggests these technologies are crucial for reducing non-value-added (NVA) activities. Similarly, AI wasn't strongly linked to productivity in this research, despite other sources (Hassan et al., 2024) highlighting AI's role in easing operator workloads to focus on higher-value tasks, ultimately increasing productivity.

These contradictions suggest two possible reasons: (1) the limited number of case studies may not be enough to capture broader industry trends, or (2) O4.0 initiatives often have overlapping objectives, making it hard to pinpoint a single primary focus. To resolve these contradictions, a larger, more comprehensive industrial survey should be conducted to capture all organisational priorities and the technologies used to achieve them. A qualitative analysis of this data could provide deeper insights into the relationships between I4.0 technologies and O4.0 objectives. Furthermore, a bibliometric analysis of a broader range of O4.0 case studies could help identify

patterns such as how AI and other technologies contribute to productivity.

The Interconnection Between I4.0 and O4.0

All case studies featured at least one I4.0 technology, reinforcing the strong interdependence between I4.0 and O4.0, as highlighted in previous research (Gladysz et al., 2023; Kaasinen et al., 2020). However, the absence of technologies like Cloud Computing, AM, Simulation, and VR suggests a selective adoption strategy rather than a comprehensive digital transformation. Alternatively, this absence may indicate a weaker alignment between these technologies and the social and human aspects of aerospace manufacturing. Conducting interviews with O4.0 implementers could help identify the reasons behind the gap in I4.0 implementation and provide insights for refining O4.0 strategies to enhance their integration into workforce-centric initiatives.

The limited adoption of VR aligns with current research (J. Pirker, 2022). Given that AR and VR are often mentioned together, this reinforces that AR has found more immediate applications in the industry. However, this contrasts with the bibliometric analysis by Gladysz et al. (2023) of O4.0 literature (Appendix P), highlighting the increasing significance of VR and simulation technologies in manufacturing. Since the study (Gladysz et al., 2023) focused on general manufacturing, its findings may not fully translate to aerospace, where industry-specific constraints could limit VR adoption. A more targeted bibliometric analysis of aerospace case studies is needed to clarify the role of VR in the sector.

Emerging Technologies

The research findings also uncovered three emerging technologies through inductive coding: Visual Computing, Digital Work Instructions, and MBD. Visual Computing is present in existing research as an umbrella term that encompasses several I4.0 technologies, including AR, VR, Computer Vision, and Visual Analytics (Segura et al., 2020).

Digital Work Instructions, falls under the broader scope of digitisation, are regarded by Zafar and Khan (2024) as “the most relevant Industry 4.0 technology in the aviation industry”, emphasising their importance for achieving operational excellence and maintaining a competitive advantage. Their role in enhancing Quality is particularly evident in the identified O4.0 case study and existing research (Dornelles, Ayala and Frank, 2021), where they streamline processes, reduce errors, and ensure consistency in manufacturing tasks. By providing operators with real-time, step-by-step guidance, Digital Work Instructions directly contribute to improved defect detection and adherence to quality standards, reinforcing their critical role in achieving Quality-focused outcomes.

Unlike these two, MBD is not currently classified within an established framework, highlighting the need for a unified taxonomy of emerging I4.0 technologies in future research. Developing a more structured categorisation through a targeted systematic literature review would simplify navigation and enhance clarity in the evolving landscape of I4.0 applications.

Pairings of I4.0 Technologies

The paired use of AI and BDA in this research’s O4.0 case studies, reinforcing their interconnected nature aligning with existing research, where Hassan et al. (2024) identify BDA as a

key “technological antecedent” of AI, serving as a foundational enabler for its development. While other pairings of I4.0 technologies were observed, the limited sample size prevents drawing definitive conclusions. Expanding the research through a bibliometric analysis of a larger dataset of case studies, as opposed to the recommendations of 4-10 by Eisenhardt (1989), can help identify additional relationships between I4.0 technologies in O4.0 applications, providing deeper insights into their complementary roles and synergies.

Gamification and Operator Data

The gamification of day-to-day tasks emerged as a theme in this research’s findings, facilitated through BDA to enhance operator motivation, self-reflection, and goal-setting. This aligns with Keepers et al. (2022), who identify motivation, efficiency, and learning as the most common benefits of gamification in industrial settings. While this research identified only two O4.0 cases implementing this approach, existing research underscores its effectiveness and growing relevance (Keepers et al., 2022). Given the potential of gamification to address social barriers to I4.0 adoption, further research focusing specifically on aerospace manufacturers through case study observations would provide valuable insights into its broader applicability and impact.

While using operator data has been seen as a valuable tool for feedback and improvement (Longo, Padovano & Umbrello, 2020; Morandini et al., 2024), the findings reveal that resistance to acting on feedback extends beyond ethical concerns. Morandini et al. (2024) also highlight additional factors, including traditional mindsets, a preference for maintaining status quo, and work-related stress which contribute to operator reluctance. Encouraging operators to adapt their traditional approach remains a complex challenge but can be mitigated through effective communication and change management strategies (Morandini et al., 2024). Further research into these two methods through interviews with industry managers will be crucial to ensuring that I4.0-driven changes are not only implemented but also sustained in the long term.

7.2 Research Methodology Discussion

Using reflexive thematic analysis and meta-synthesis of case studies, combined with both inductive and deductive coding in Nvivo 15, proved to be a powerful method for uncovering key contextual themes and generating insights into O4.0 and I4.0. This approach allowed for a flexible and comprehensive exploration of emerging technologies without being restricted by predefined categories, as demonstrated by the use of Culot et al. (2020)’s I4.0 framework. The decision not to follow a strict list of technologies enabled the identification of additional key technologies such as artificial intelligence, visual computing, and digitisation

However, several limitations must be acknowledged. While the case studies’ sample size (10) allowed for in-depth qualitative analysis, it restricted the ability to generalise findings to broader industry trends. The reliance on secondary data further compounded this limitation, as some case studies lacked critical details, such as company names, geographical context, and specifics on technology implementation. This absence of key contextual information weakened the robustness of cross-case comparisons, making it more challenging to derive industry-wide conclusions. While prioritising case studies with complete data could improve future research, the early-stage nature

of O4.0 research makes finding such comprehensive cases challenging – with the growing nature of the topic, this could set to change.

Another limitation was the breadth of insights generated. While diverse themes emerged, the wide-ranging nature of the findings risked diluting the depth of analysis. Refining the research focus for instance, by examining specific I4.0 technologies and their direct impact on O4.0 could yield more targeted and actionable conclusions. Additionally, conducting cross-industry comparisons, particularly between aerospace and other manufacturing sectors such as automotive and electronics, could help differentiate industry-specific challenges from broader technological trends.

Finally, while thematic analysis was effective in identifying qualitative patterns, the study could have been strengthened by methodological triangulation. Integrating quantitative approaches, such as structured surveys or expert interviews, would help validate findings, reduce potential biases from secondary data sources, and provide a more balanced understanding of O4.0 adoption. Future research should consider mixed-method approaches to improve the reliability and applicability of insights in this evolving field.

7.3 Discussion Conclusion

This discussion has critically examined the implementation of O4.0 within aerospace manufacturing, highlighting key themes such as complexity, quality, safety, operator demand, and productivity. While O4.0 is often presented as a transformative framework, findings suggest that its adoption remains fragmented, with a selective rather than holistic integration of I4.0 technologies. The misalignment between industry expectations and practical realities underscores the challenges of fully embedding I4.0 in such a high-complexity environment.

Key contradictions have emerged, particularly regarding the prioritisation of quality and the limited role of safety-focused digitalisation. Additionally, while productivity remains a primary driver, the absence of widely acknowledged efficiency-enhancing technologies, such as AI and cobots, raises concerns about the true extent of digital transformation. The interconnection between I4.0 and O4.0 is evident, yet the absence of advanced digital solutions like Cloud Computing and VR suggests that technological feasibility alone does not guarantee adoption to O4.0.

The discussion also highlights emerging research gaps, including the need for longitudinal studies assessing the scalability of O4.0 implementations, a more structured taxonomy of new I4.0 technologies, and an investigation into the psychological impact of digitalisation on operators. Furthermore, methodological reflections indicate that while reflexive thematic analysis provided depth, future research should incorporate broader triangulated approaches to enhance validity and generalisability.

Ultimately, this study contributes to a critical discourse on O4.0 and I4.0, calling for a more nuanced understanding of its impact on aerospace manufacturing. To bridge the gap between theory and practice, future research must address both technical and human factors, ensuring that O4.0 fulfils its full potential.

8 Conclusion

The primary aim of this research was to identify the key barriers to I4.0 adoption in aerospace manufacturing and to propose a strategy to navigate its complexities. To achieve this, a multi-stage approach was carried out encompassing a comprehensive literature review, a structured methodological design, empirical analysis, and a critical discussion of findings.

The literature review established that I4.0 represents a fundamental shift in manufacturing driven by technologies such as AI, BDA, and IIoT. However, despite its transformative potential, aerospace is still lagging behind other sectors in adopting these advancements. The review identified key barriers and enablers across organisational, technological, strategic, and sustainability dimensions, highlighting the emerging O4.0 paradigm as a means to address human and social challenges in digital transformation.

While the literature provided valuable theoretical insights, there were still gaps in understanding how these barriers translate into practice, warranting further investigation. To address this, the study used a reflexive thematic analysis of qualitative case studies, with a hybrid inductive-deductive coding approach to explore O4.0 adoption in aerospace manufacturing. While effective in capturing industry-specific insights, the methodology had certain limitations, including a small sample size (10 cases), reliance on secondary data, and thematic breadth at the expense of analytical depth. Nonetheless, it provided valuable perspectives on O4.0 implementation challenges, reinforcing known barriers while uncovering new insights:

- While some technologies, such as AR and AI-driven analytics, were commonly employed, others such as Cloud Computing and VR remained underutilised.
- Safety, was weakly integrated with O4.0 initiatives, suggesting a reliance on traditional safety methods or a disconnect between regulatory compliance and digital innovation.
- The findings highlighted the increasing cognitive load on operators, contradicting the assumption that O4.0 inherently reduces human strain.
- The research identified a need for clearer categorisation of new technologies such as MBD, which currently lack a structured framework for implementation.

The discussion chapter contextualised these findings, drawing attention to discrepancies between industry claims and practical implementation. Several critical reflections emerged:

- O4.0 is often portrayed as transformative, but its adoption remains selective and fragmented suggesting that O4.0 remains an evolving concept rather than a fully realised framework in aerospace manufacturing.
- Quality was a dominant theme, but inconsistencies between regulatory requirements and operational realities suggest that other factors, such as innovation or profits, often take precedence.
- Operator resistance to data-driven insights suggests that technical solutions alone are insufficient to successful adoption and in cases are increasing cognitive load rather than reducing it - therefore counterproductive.

- There is a need for further research on the psychological impact of O4.0 technologies on operators, as well as longitudinal studies on the scalability and long-term effects of O4.0 adoption. The lack of a structured taxonomy for emerging technologies like MBD also calls for further academic attention.
- The research methodology, primarily using reflexive thematic analysis, was effective in uncovering nuanced industry insights but was limited by a small sample size and reliance on secondary data. Future research should seek to incorporate broader triangulated approaches to improve the validity and generalisability of findings.

Although the aim of proposing a comprehensive strategy was not fully realised, the study's findings offer a crucial starting point for the aerospace manufacturing sector. This research not only identifies the transformative potential of I4.0 but also lays an innovative foundation and solution to bridge the gap between technological advancement and human-centric integration. Future research should continue to build on these insights to inform industry implementation strategies, bridging the gap between the current state of O4.0 adoption and its full potential.

9 Limitations and Future Research

9.1 Limitations

Limited Case Study Sample and Generalisability

The study analysed a relatively small number of case studies (10), which, while sufficient for exploratory research, limits the robustness of broader industry-wide conclusions. A larger dataset would enhance the statistical confidence and allow for more nuanced differentiation between the impact of various I4.0 technologies. Furthermore, the findings may not fully capture regional or organisational variations in O4.0 implementation. Given that case studies inherently reflect specific organisational priorities and operational constraints, a more diverse sample including firms at different digital transformation stages would offer a clearer picture of O4.0's scalability and adoption patterns.

Sector-Specific Constraints

By focusing exclusively on aerospace manufacturing, this research provides deep industry-specific insights but at the expense of cross-sector comparability. Aerospace is characterised by stringent regulatory demands, highly customised production lower automation levels relative to sectors such as automotive or consumer electronics. These factors influence the adoption of O4.0 in ways that may not be applicable elsewhere. Consequently, the findings cannot be readily extrapolated to industries with higher production volumes or different regulatory frameworks. Future comparative studies across multiple sectors would be essential in distinguishing universal O4.0 adoption patterns from aerospace-specific challenges.

Reliance on Secondary Data and Methods

This study primarily utilised secondary data sources and surveys, limiting direct observational verification. While secondary sources provide a broad overview, they inherently risk selec-

tion bias, where certain narratives such as the prioritisation of quality over safety are over- or underrepresented. Notably, the finding that safety was the least emphasised theme in O4.0 implementation raises concerns: Is safety truly deprioritised, or is it being managed outside the scope of digital transformation initiatives? Without in-person observations, it is difficult to be certain whether manufacturers integrate safety through conventional, non-digital means or if its absence reflects a genuine gap in O4.0 strategies. Future research should incorporate ethnographic methods and site visits to validate these conclusions.

Methodological Constraints and Thematic Oversimplification

The research was guided by Eisenhardt's (1989) case study synthesis framework, which suggests 4–10 cases. However, while this framework provided structure, it may have inadvertently simplified the complexity of O4.0 implementation. The multifaceted interactions between I4.0 technologies, human factors, and organisational priorities are not easily captured through case studies alone. Additionally, by grouping findings under broad thematic categories (e.g., quality, productivity, safety), the study risks oversimplifying interdependencies between these factors. A more granular, longitudinal approach that tracks O4.0 adoption over time would provide deeper insights into the trajectory of digital transformation in aerospace manufacturing.

9.2 Future Research

Building on the limitations identified in this study, future research must adopt a more expansive, interdisciplinary, and empirically grounded approach to enhance the validity and applicability of O4.0 insights in aerospace manufacturing. Several key research priorities emerge:

Expanding the Dataset for Greater Generalisability

A significantly larger and more representative dataset spanning various organisational sizes, geographic regions, and digital maturity levels is needed. Longitudinal studies would provide insights into how O4.0 adoption evolves over time and whether initial implementation challenges persist or diminish. Moreover, employing a mixed-methods approach that combines case study analysis, structured surveys, and expert interviews would enhance the depth and triangulation of findings, mitigating the risks of secondary data reliance.

Cross-Sectoral Comparisons to Identify Transferable Insights

Comparative studies between aerospace and industries such as automotive, pharmaceuticals, and electronics can help identify industry-specific constraints versus broader technological trends. Additionally, contrasting low-volume, high-customisation production environments with mass-production industries would provide a clearer understanding of how production scale influences O4.0 implementation strategies. These comparisons would help refine best practices and facilitate knowledge transfer between industries.

Establishing a Structured Taxonomy of O4.0 and I4.0 Technologies

The absence of a clear taxonomy creates confusion for both academics and practitioners. Future research should conduct a bibliometric analysis of O4.0 case studies to establish a unified classification system for I4.0 technologies, clarifying their respective roles within digital manufacturing.

This would provide a clearer roadmap for organisations navigating O4.0 adoption.

Investigating the Absence of Key I4.0 Technologies in O4.0 Applications

Several major I4.0 technologies including Cloud Computing, AM, Simulations and VR were notably absent from the O4.0 case studies examined. Future research should explore why these technologies have yet to gain traction in O4.0 initiatives and whether specific factors are impeding their adoption. Understanding these barriers would allow firms to refine their digital transformation strategies and accelerate O4.0 implementation.

Addressing Operator Resistance to Digital Feedback Mechanisms

Findings indicate that while O4.0 technologies facilitate increased performance monitoring, operator resistance to data-driven feedback remains a critical challenge. Psychological and behavioural factors including traditional mindsets and work-related stress contribute to this resistance (Morandini et al., 2024). Future research should examine change management strategies and communication techniques that foster greater acceptance of data-driven decision-making.

Evaluating the Role of Gamification in Operator Engagement

While gamification has demonstrated effectiveness in other industrial sectors (Keepers et al., 2022), its impact in aerospace manufacturing remains largely unexplored. Future research should investigate whether gamification can serve as a bridge between digital transformation efforts and workforce engagement, particularly in overcoming cultural and social barriers to I4.0 adoption. A structured assessment of gamification strategies ranging from simple reward systems to immersive, game-based training could provide insights into how digital engagement techniques can be optimally deployed within high-complexity manufacturing environments.

Overall, addressing these research gaps would provide deeper insights into the evolving role of I4.0 and O4.0 in aerospace manufacturing, ensuring that digital transformation strategies align more effectively with both technological advancements and human social factors.

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11 Appendix

11.1 Appendix A

I4.0 Enabling Technology	Definition
<i>Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT)</i>	A network enabling communication between machines and devices (Tabaković and Duraković, 2021) and the artificial world to people (Aydin and Kahraman, 2022). It uses sensors and information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure to achieve real-time sensing and actuating capabilities (Bajjic et al., 2021). IIoT is a subset of the broader Internet of Things (IoT), with a specific focus on industrial applications (Bhatia et al., 2024).
<i>System Integration</i>	System Integration refers to the seamless connection and coordination of various systems and processes across different departments or companies (horizontal) and systems at different hierarchical levels within the same organization (vertical) (Aydin and Kahraman, 2022; Bhatia et al., 2024).
<i>Additive Manufacturing (AM)</i>	Additive Manufacturing represents the process of object fabrication by joining materials layer-by-layer (Carou, 2021; Tabaković and Duraković, 2021) rather than subtractive manufacturing technologies (Bhatia et al., 2024). Based on digital information, three-dimensional objects are produced on demand (Bajjic et al., 2021).
<i>Autonomous Robots</i>	Intelligent machines capable of performing tasks independently without explicit human control (Bhatia et al., 2024). This includes collaborative robots, or 'cobots', which enable humans and machines to work together in a shared learning environment (Tabaković and Duraković, 2021).
<i>Cloud Computing</i>	A vast, flexible, and decentralized pool of storage, services, and computational capabilities (Bhatia et al., 2024), accessible to users at any time via the Internet (Aydin and Kahraman, 2022).
<i>Big Data Analytics (BDA)</i>	The collection and analysis of large amounts of data (Aydin and Kahraman, 2022) through innovative forms of information processing for enhanced insight and real-time decision-making (Bajjic et al., 2021; Tabaković and Duraković, 2021).
<i>Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR)</i>	The overlay of computer graphics on real-life operations (AR) (Tabaković and Duraković, 2021) to alter reality, or even to create a new one (VR) (Carou, 2021) providing human interaction with virtual space (Bajjic et al., 2021).
<i>Simulation</i>	Use of digital models to replicate physical processes, systems, or environments. This allows for experimentation, testing, and optimization of products, processes, and systems before actual implementation (Bhatia et al., 2024; Carou, 2021).
<i>Cyber Security</i>	The implementation of technology, policies and organizational practices to protect computers, networks, software programs, and data (Bhatia et al., 2024) from attacks, unauthorized access, alterations, or destruction (Bajjic et al., 2021).

Nine Pillars of I4.0 and Definitions from Literature (Source: Author)

11.2 Appendix B

I4.0 Patent Analysis (Bhatia et al., 2024)

11.3 Appendix C

O4.0 Scopus search analysis (Source: Author)

11.4 Appendix D

Typology	Description	Source
<i>Super-strength</i>	An operator that uses exoskeletons: wearable technologies designed to enhance physical strength, enabling experienced operators with aging or disabilities to remain in critical roles while leveraging their expertise.	(Nuijen et al., 2024; Gladysz et al., 2023; Kaasinen et al., 2020)
<i>Augmented Operator and Virtual Operator</i>	An operator that uses AR/VR to simulate realistic scenarios, such as product assembly, by transforming CAD models into interactive virtual simulations. These tools aid in training for complex tasks, enabling operators to explore decision outcomes safely without risking themselves or the environment.	(Nuijen et al., 2024; J. Pirker, 2022; Gladysz et al., 2023; Kaasinen et al., 2020)
<i>Smart Operator</i>	An operator that uses intelligent personal assistants (IPAs), powered by artificial intelligence, to help interface with machines, databases, and information systems, manage time commitments, and perform tasks through human-like interactions. A key feature is voice interaction technology, enabling hands-free task completion.	(Nuijen et al., 2024; Hassan et al., 2024; Gladysz et al., 2023; Kaasinen et al., 2020)
<i>Collaborative Operator</i>	An operator that uses cobots to assist in performing repetitive and non-ergonomic tasks. Equipped with safety and intuitive interaction technologies, cobots work alongside humans in shared workspaces without traditional safety barriers. They enhance productivity and job satisfaction by enabling operators to work more effectively while alleviating tedious and physically demanding tasks.	(Nuijen et al., 2024; Carou, 2021; Gladysz et al., 2023; Kaasinen et al., 2020)
<i>Healthy Operator</i>	An operator that uses wearable devices, like fitness trackers or smartwatches, to monitor well-being by tracking biometric data such as heart rate, physical activity, and cognitive workload. These devices can identify stressful work conditions, prompt health-based scheduling of shifts and breaks, and provide alerts to manage occupational effort, promoting better health and productivity.	(Nuijen et al., 2024; Bhatia et al., 2024; Gladysz et al., 2023; Kaasinen et al., 2020)
<i>Social Operator</i>	An operator that utilizes social networks, such as the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), to enhance communication between humans and machines. These networks facilitate information sharing, decision-making, and problem-solving, improving material flow, resource productivity, and identifying bottlenecks in production.	(Nuijen et al., 2024; Carou, 2021; Gladysz et al., 2023; Kaasinen et al., 2020)
<i>Analytic Operator</i>	An operator that uses BDA to collect and analyse large data sets to gain insights and predict scenarios. This technology enhances forecasting, shop/floor control, and continuous improvement. Real-time analysis can also provide warnings about potential safety risks to operators.	(Nuijen et al., 2024; Carou, 2021; Gladysz et al., 2023; Kaasinen et al., 2020)

O4.0 Typology from Literature (Source: Author)

11.5 Appendix E

	Step/Phase	Description
(Byrne, 2022)	1 Familiarisation	This initial phase involves immersing yourself in the data by reading and re-reading it to become deeply familiar with its content. This helps in identifying initial ideas and patterns. In this phase, you systematically code interesting features of the data across the entire dataset. This involves organizing the data into meaningful groups and tagging segments of the data with labels (codes).
	2 Generating Initial Codes	Here, you collate codes into potential themes. This phase involves sorting the different codes into themes and gathering all the relevant data for each potential theme.
	3 Generating Themes	During this phase, you refine the themes by reviewing and refining them to ensure they accurately represent the data. This may involve merging, splitting, or discarding themes to ensure they are coherent and distinct.
	4 Reviewing Potential Themes	In this phase, you define and name each theme. This involves identifying the essence of each theme and determining what aspect of the data each theme captures. Clear definitions and names are created for each theme.
	5 Defining and Naming Themes	The final phase involves writing up the analysis. This includes weaving together the narrative of the data with the themes, providing vivid examples, and making a compelling argument that answers the research question.
	6 Producing the Report	This initial step involves clearly defining the research question that guides the meta-synthesis. It sets the direction for the entire study.
(Hoon, 2013)	1 Framing the Research Question	In this phase, relevant qualitative case studies are identified and gathered. This involves comprehensive literature searches to find studies that address the research question.
	2 Locating Relevant Research	Criteria are established to determine which studies will be included or excluded from the synthesis. This ensures that only relevant and high-quality studies are considered.
	3 Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria	Data from the selected studies are systematically extracted and coded. This involves identifying key themes, concepts, and findings that are pertinent to the research question.
	4 Extracting and Coding Data	Each case study is analyzed individually to understand its unique contributions and insights. This helps in identifying specific patterns and themes within each study.
	5 Analyzing on a Case-Specific Level	The findings from individual case studies are synthesized across studies to identify common patterns, themes, and relationships. This step integrates the insights from multiple studies.
	6 Synthesis on a Cross-Study Level	Based on the synthesized findings, a theoretical framework is developed. This framework helps in explaining the relationships and patterns identified in the data.
(PRISMA, 2020)	7 Building Theory from Meta-Synthesis	The final step involves discussing the synthesized findings and the theoretical framework. This includes interpreting the results, discussing their implications, and suggesting directions for future research.
	8 Discussion	Specifies the characteristics used to decide whether a study is included in the review, such as study design, participants, interventions, and outcomes.
	1 Eligibility Criteria	Lists all databases, registers, websites, organizations, and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies, along with the dates when each source was last searched.
	2 Information Sources	Provides the full search strategies for all databases, registers, and websites, including any filters and limits used.
	3 Search Strategy	Describes the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria, including how many reviewers screened each record and report, and any automation tools used.
	4 Selection Process	Details the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data, whether they worked independently, and any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators.
	5 Data Collection Process	Lists and defines all outcomes and other variables for which data were sought, and describes any assumptions made about missing or unclear information.
	6 Data Items	Specifies the tools and methods used to assess the risk of bias in the included studies, including how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently.
	7 Study Risk of Bias Assessment	Specifies the effect measures (e.g., risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results for each outcome.
	8 Effect Measures	Describes the methods used to decide which studies were eligible for synthesis, prepare data for synthesis, and conduct statistical synthesis, including handling of heterogeneity and sensitivity analyses.
	9 Synthesis Methods	Specifies the methods used to assess the risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis, such as funnel plots or statistical tests for funnel plot asymmetry.
10 Reporting Bias Assessment	Specifies the tools and criteria used to assess the certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence, including factors considered and decision rules used to arrive at an overall judgement.	
11 Certainty Assessment		

Phase Overview (Source: Author)

11.6 Appendix F

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases and registers only

*Consider, if feasible to do so, reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched (rather than the total number across all databases/registers).

**If automation tools were used, indicate how many records were excluded by a human and how many were excluded by automation tools.

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. BMJ 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. This work is licensed under CC BY 4.0. To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

PRISMA Flowchart and Checklist (PRISMA, 2020)

11.7 Appendix G

or data items that inform these themes may be incongruent and require revision. Braun and Clarke (2012, p. 65) proposed a series of key questions that the researcher should address when reviewing potential themes. They are:

- Is this a theme (it could be just a code)?
- If it is a theme, what is the quality of this theme (does it tell me something useful about the data set and my research question)?
- What are the boundaries of this theme (what does it include and exclude)?
- Are there enough (meaningful) data to support this theme (is the theme thin or thick)?
- Are the data too diverse and wide ranging (does the theme lack coherence)?

Braun and Clarke Key Questions (Byrne, 2022)

11.8 Appendix H

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
AR complex	1	1	27/12/2024 17:01	MS	27/12/2024 17:01	MS
AR environment affecting performance	1	1	26/12/2024 12:50	MS	26/12/2024 12:50	MS
AR for training	1	1	26/12/2024 15:28	MS	27/12/2024 11:44	MS
AR markers disrupting locations	1	1	26/12/2024 12:49	MS	26/12/2024 12:49	MS
artificial intelligence	3	3	26/12/2024 11:33	MS	27/12/2024 11:20	MS
augmented reality	4	4	26/12/2024 12:13	MS	27/12/2024 12:32	MS
better decision making	3	3	27/12/2024 11:06	MS	27/12/2024 12:36	MS
big data analytics	6	6	26/12/2024 11:53	MS	27/12/2024 17:54	MS
cobot	2	2	26/12/2024 11:32	MS	26/12/2024 12:16	MS
complex aircraft	1	1	26/12/2024 11:26	MS	26/12/2024 11:26	MS
complex part geometry	1	1	26/12/2024 11:56	MS	26/12/2024 11:56	MS
complex parts	2	2	27/12/2024 11:33	MS	27/12/2024 17:43	MS
complex processes	1	1	27/12/2024 11:33	MS	27/12/2024 11:33	MS
cycle time reduction	3	4	26/12/2024 11:45	MS	27/12/2024 17:39	MS
dangerous working environment	1	1	26/12/2024 11:25	MS	26/12/2024 11:25	MS
data increases awareness of behaviours	2	2	26/12/2024 14:25	MS	27/12/2024 18:24	MS
data used for self-reflection	1	1	26/12/2024 14:24	MS	26/12/2024 14:24	MS
database	1	1	26/12/2024 11:53	MS	26/12/2024 11:53	MS
defect detection	2	2	26/12/2024 11:34	MS	26/12/2024 12:46	MS
defect risk	1	1	26/12/2024 11:57	MS	26/12/2024 11:57	MS
digital work instruction	1	1	26/12/2024 12:14	MS	26/12/2024 12:14	MS
diverse processes	3	4	26/12/2024 15:17	MS	27/12/2024 17:43	MS
eager to adopt	2	2	26/12/2024 12:47	MS	26/12/2024 14:35	MS
ergonomic risks	1	1	26/12/2024 11:29	MS	26/12/2024 11:30	MS

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
gamification	2	3	27/12/2024 11:18	MS	27/12/2024 17:41	MS
high AR usability	1	1	26/12/2024 12:41	MS	26/12/2024 12:41	MS
high cost	1	1	26/12/2024 11:59	MS	26/12/2024 11:59	MS
high demand on operator ability	2	4	26/12/2024 15:21	MS	27/12/2024 11:38	MS
high part weight	1	1	26/12/2024 12:18	MS	26/12/2024 12:18	MS
high usefulness	1	1	26/12/2024 12:43	MS	26/12/2024 12:43	MS
horizontal vertical integration	1	1	27/12/2024 11:36	MS	27/12/2024 11:36	MS
I4.0 awareness	1	1	27/12/2024 17:00	MS	27/12/2024 17:00	MS
I4.0 for inspection	3	3	26/12/2024 11:31	MS	27/12/2024 17:37	MS
importance of quality	2	2	26/12/2024 15:24	MS	27/12/2024 17:45	MS
improved accessibility	2	2	26/12/2024 11:51	MS	27/12/2024 10:51	MS
improved defect detection	0	0	26/12/2024 13:27	MS	26/12/2024 13:27	MS
improved ergonomics	2	2	26/12/2024 11:51	MS	27/12/2024 17:38	MS
improved health	1	1	27/12/2024 17:38	MS	27/12/2024 17:38	MS
improved hierarchical communication	2	2	26/12/2024 12:55	MS	27/12/2024 18:25	MS
improved operator wellbeing	2	2	26/12/2024 11:44	MS	26/12/2024 14:33	MS
improved profitability	1	1	27/12/2024 17:40	MS	27/12/2024 17:40	MS
improved training phases	1	1	27/12/2024 17:39	MS	27/12/2024 17:39	MS
increased autonomy	3	3	26/12/2024 11:52	MS	27/12/2024 12:03	MS
increased motivation	2	2	26/12/2024 14:34	MS	27/12/2024 17:38	MS
increased safety	3	3	26/12/2024 11:35	MS	27/12/2024 12:35	MS
IoT	3	4	27/12/2024 11:20	MS	27/12/2024 12:35	MS
lack of confidence	1	1	27/12/2024 17:02	MS	27/12/2024 17:02	MS
lack of customisation	1	1	27/12/2024 17:03	MS	27/12/2024 17:03	MS

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
long assembly times	1	1	26/12/2024 15:30	MS	26/12/2024 15:30	MS
manual process	3	3	26/12/2024 11:56	MS	27/12/2024 11:50	MS
model based definition	1	1	26/12/2024 15:17	MS	26/12/2024 15:17	MS
New Code	0	0	27/12/2024 17:41	MS	27/12/2024 17:41	MS
no health and productivity support	1	1	27/12/2024 11:40	MS	27/12/2024 11:40	MS
operator data misuse concerns	1	1	26/12/2024 14:30	MS	26/12/2024 14:59	MS
operator driven	1	1	26/12/2024 11:43	MS	26/12/2024 11:43	MS
operator learning	1	1	26/12/2024 15:22	MS	26/12/2024 15:22	MS
operator production feedback improves motivation for better performance	1	1	26/12/2024 14:21	MS	26/12/2024 14:21	MS
operator resistance	1	1	26/12/2024 14:28	MS	26/12/2024 14:28	MS
operator stress	1	1	26/12/2024 11:30	MS	26/12/2024 11:30	MS
operator training	1	1	26/12/2024 12:15	MS	26/12/2024 12:15	MS
operators feel controlled	1	1	26/12/2024 14:29	MS	26/12/2024 14:29	MS
operators not concerned about data security	1	1	26/12/2024 14:27	MS	26/12/2024 14:27	MS
operators value feedback	1	1	26/12/2024 14:22	MS	26/12/2024 14:22	MS
PLM system integration	1	1	26/12/2024 12:52	MS	26/12/2024 12:52	MS
reduced defect rate	2	2	26/12/2024 12:33	MS	27/12/2024 11:52	MS
reduced human intervention	2	2	26/12/2024 11:35	MS	27/12/2024 12:03	MS
reduced NVA	1	1	26/12/2024 12:34	MS	26/12/2024 12:34	MS
reduced operator cognitive workload	1	1	26/12/2024 15:34	MS	26/12/2024 15:34	MS
reduced physical workload	2	2	26/12/2024 12:29	MS	27/12/2024 11:04	MS
reduced waste	1	1	26/12/2024 12:32	MS	26/12/2024 12:32	MS

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
remote AR training	1	1	27/12/2024 11:44	MS	27/12/2024 11:44	MS
required operator body type	1	1	26/12/2024 11:28	MS	26/12/2024 11:28	MS
sensors	1	1	26/12/2024 11:33	MS	26/12/2024 11:33	MS
sleep and exercise have positive impact on work well-being	1	1	26/12/2024 14:26	MS	26/12/2024 14:26	MS
specialised operators	2	2	26/12/2024 11:57	MS	27/12/2024 11:35	MS
strict tolerance	2	2	26/12/2024 11:58	MS	27/12/2024 11:34	MS
tight working space	2	2	26/12/2024 11:27	MS	27/12/2024 10:49	MS
visual computing	1	2	27/12/2024 11:49	MS	27/12/2024 11:59	MS

Initial Coding (Source: Author)

11.9 Appendix I

Case-Specific Analysis Concept Maps (Source: Author)

11.10 Appendix J

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
Aerospace Manufacturing	6	33	31/12/2024 12:48	MS	06/01/2025 12:26	MS
Aerospace Complexity	4	8	03/01/2025 11:21	MS	14/01/2025 11:04	MS
Complex Aircraft	1	1	26/12/2024 11:26	MS	14/01/2025 11:03	MS
Complex Parts	3	6	27/12/2024 11:33	MS	14/01/2025 11:03	MS
Complex Processes	1	1	27/12/2024 11:33	MS	14/01/2025 11:04	MS
Aerospace Environment	6	16	03/01/2025 11:22	MS	14/01/2025 11:04	MS
Dangerous Working Envi	2	4	26/12/2024 11:25	MS	14/01/2025 11:05	MS
Diverse Processes	3	4	26/12/2024 15:17	MS	14/01/2025 11:04	MS
High Cost	1	1	26/12/2024 11:59	MS	14/01/2025 11:05	MS
Importance of Quality	2	2	26/12/2024 15:24	MS	03/01/2025 12:49	MS
Long Assembly Times	1	1	26/12/2024 15:30	MS	14/01/2025 11:05	MS
Manual Process	3	3	26/12/2024 11:56	MS	14/01/2025 11:05	MS
Health and Productivity	1	1	27/12/2024 11:40	MS	14/01/2025 11:06	MS
Operator Ability Demand	4	9	26/12/2024 15:21	MS	14/01/2025 11:04	MS
Defect Risk	1	1	26/12/2024 11:57	MS	14/01/2025 11:06	MS
Operator Stress	1	1	26/12/2024 11:30	MS	14/01/2025 11:06	MS
Specialised Operators	3	3	26/12/2024 11:57	MS	14/01/2025 11:06	MS

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
Industry 4.0	10	53	31/12/2024 12:50	MS	13/01/2025 16:16	MS
Artificial Intelligence (AI)	3	3	26/12/2024 11:33	MS	14/01/2025 11:02	MS
AI for AM	1	1	03/01/2025 11:51	MS	13/01/2025 16:16	MS
AI for ergonomics	1	1	03/01/2025 11:50	MS	13/01/2025 16:16	MS
AI for inspection	1	1	03/01/2025 11:51	MS	13/01/2025 16:16	MS
Augmented Reality (AR)	6	12	26/12/2024 12:13	MS	14/01/2025 11:02	MS
AR awareness	1	1	27/12/2024 17:00	MS	13/01/2025 16:16	MS
AR Complex	2	4	27/12/2024 17:01	MS	13/01/2025 16:16	MS
AR for Training	1	1	26/12/2024 15:28	MS	13/01/2025 16:16	MS
High AR Usability	1	1	26/12/2024 12:41	MS	14/01/2025 11:02	MS
High AR Usefulness	1	1	26/12/2024 12:43	MS	14/01/2025 11:07	MS
Big Data Analytics (BDA)	6	15	26/12/2024 11:53	MS	14/01/2025 11:03	MS
Database	1	1	26/12/2024 11:53	MS	14/01/2025 11:07	MS
Gamification	2	8	27/12/2024 11:18	MS	14/01/2025 11:07	MS
Cobot	2	5	26/12/2024 11:32	MS	14/01/2025 11:09	MS
Horizontal Vertical Integratio	2	2	27/12/2024 11:36	MS	14/01/2025 11:09	MS
PLM system integration	1	1	26/12/2024 12:51	MS	13/01/2025 16:16	MS

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
I4.0 Emerging	4	6	03/01/2025 11:52	MS	14/01/2025 11:10	MS
Digital Work Instruction	3	3	26/12/2024 12:14	MS	14/01/2025 11:08	MS
Model Based Definition	1	1	26/12/2024 15:17	MS	14/01/2025 11:08	MS
Visual Computing	1	2	27/12/2024 11:49	MS	14/01/2025 11:08	MS
I4.0 for Inspection	3	5	26/12/2024 11:31	MS	14/01/2025 11:10	MS
Defect Detection	2	2	26/12/2024 11:34	MS	14/01/2025 11:08	MS
IoT	4	5	27/12/2024 11:20	MS	14/01/2025 11:10	MS

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
Operator	7	15	31/12/2024 13:22	MS	06/01/2025 12:26	MS
Eager to Adopt I4.0	2	2	26/12/2024 12:47	MS	14/01/2025 11:12	MS
Lack of Confidence	1	1	27/12/2024 17:02	MS	14/01/2025 11:13	MS
Operator Data	2	8	03/01/2025 11:53	MS	14/01/2025 11:14	MS
Operator Empowered	1	1	26/12/2024 11:43	MS	14/01/2025 11:14	MS
Operator Resistance	1	1	26/12/2024 14:28	MS	14/01/2025 11:14	MS
Operator Training	2	2	26/12/2024 12:15	MS	14/01/2025 11:15	MS

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
Outcome	9	34	03/01/2025 11:56	MS	14/01/2025 11:16	MS
Operator Outcome	7	18	03/01/2025 12:35	MS	14/01/2025 11:16	MS
Improved Health	1	1	27/12/2024 17:38	MS	14/01/2025 11:15	MS
Improved Wellbeing	2	2	26/12/2024 11:44	MS	04/01/2025 11:56	MS
Increased Safety	5	7	03/01/2025 12:11	MS	03/01/2025 12:25	MS
Reduced Workload	4	8	03/01/2025 12:09	MS	03/01/2025 12:23	MS
Organisational Outcome	8	16	03/01/2025 12:36	MS	14/01/2025 11:16	MS
Improved Hierarchical Co	3	3	26/12/2024 12:55	MS	03/01/2025 12:44	MS
Improved Training Phases	1	1	27/12/2024 17:39	MS	03/01/2025 12:46	MS
Increased Profitability	1	1	27/12/2024 17:40	MS	03/01/2025 12:45	MS
Reduced Waste	6	11	26/12/2024 12:32	MS	14/01/2025 11:17	MS
Better Decision Maki	3	3	27/12/2024 11:06	MS	14/01/2025 11:16	MS
Cycle Time Reduction	3	4	26/12/2024 11:45	MS	14/01/2025 11:16	MS
Reduced Defect Rate	2	2	26/12/2024 12:33	MS	14/01/2025 11:16	MS
Reduced NVA	1	1	26/12/2024 12:34	MS	14/01/2025 11:16	MS

Generating Themes and Patton's First Review (Source: Author)

11.11 Appendix K

Cross-Study Concept Map (Source: Author)

11.12 Appendix L

Patton's Second Review and Naming Themes (Source: Author)

11.13 Appendix M

Double click theme/code/subcode from concept map (left) or codebook (right) to reveal below.

<Files\Assessment Tool for Digital Enhancement of Operators> - 3 references coded [0.18% Coverage]

References 1-2 - 0.06% Coverage

Complex product and process characteristics

Reference 3 - 0.12% Coverage

with high precision requirements, a large number of discrete manufacturing processes

<Files\Enhancing Additive Manufacturing Post-Process> - 3 references coded [0.42% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.06% Coverage

producing parts with complex geometries

Reference 2 - 0.22% Coverage

It is a difficult process as there is a high chance that the operator damages the part during the support removal as the tolerances are strict.

Reference 3 - 0.14% Coverage

manipulation of parts of high weight and the difficulty of mounting them on milling machines

Viewing NVivo Codes, Subcodes and Sources (Source: Author)

11.14 Appendix N

Source	Title	Company	Type	Primary Org Focus	Background	14.0 Tech	Takeaways	Operator 4.0 Archetype
Dimitropoulos, N. et al. (2024a)	Improving Aircraft Fuel Tank Maintenance	n/a	Use Case	Safety	Improving maintenance tasks inside aircraft fuel tank, defect detection. Tight working space requires specific operator body type. Replacing operator with cobot arm.	Cobots, BDA, AI, IoT	Increased autonomy. Increased safety. Improved Operator Wellbeing. Reduced NVA. Improved Ergonomics. AR tools to facilitate HRI with digital work instructions. Data collection for trained AI model.	Collaborative Operator, Smart Operator
Dimitropoulos, N. et al. (2024b)	Enhancing Additive Manufacturing Post-Processing	n/a	Use Case	Quality	Aiding operator in post processing of AM for complex part geometry, defect detection. Manual process, high part weight manoeuvres and high costs for surface finishing.	Cobots, BDA, AI	Improve ergonomics. Increase autonomy. Operator can train cobot. Data to train AI model.	Collaborative Operator, Smart Operator
Barbieri, L. et al. (2024)	User-centered design of an augmented reality inspection tool for Industry 4.0 operators	Baker Hughes	Questionnaire	Quality	Augmented Reality tool designed to streamline real-time inspection activities performed by operators on assembled products at the workplace.	AR, System Integration	Improved communication. Improved defect detection. Integration of tool with PLM, Added to Nvivo.	Augmented Operator, Social Operator
Heikkilä, P. et al. (2021)	Web application supporting work well-being and productivity	(Unnamed)	Interviews	Productivity	Worker Feedback Dashboard web application to offer factory floor workers data-driven near-real-time feedback of metrics related to their well-being and work achievements.	BDA	Improved motivation. Improved well-being. Added to Nvivo.	Healthy Operator, Analytic Operator
Li, D. (2022)	Final Assembly Model-Based Definition Goggles	(Unnamed)	Observations	Productivity	Use of AR goggles to overlay 3D models for operator use in product assembly. Reducing distance between operator and computer with instructions.	AR	Increased autonomy. Reduced cognitive workload. Decreased cycle time. Reduced physical workload. Improved decision making. AR for training purposes. Added to Nvivo.	Augmented Operator, Social Operator
Pinzone, M. et al. (2021)	Digitally Enhanced Operator Assessment Tool	GKN Aerospace	Observations	Productivity	Identifying opportunities to enhance digital operator through data analytics, smartwatches and AR glasses	AR, BDA, System Integration, IoT	Added to Nvivo.	Augmented Operator, Healthy Operator, Analytic Operator, Social Operator
Posada, J. (2021)	In-Line Dimensional Inspection with 3D Reconstruction	(Unnamed)	Observations	Quality	3D mesh reconstruction of hot workpiece performed using blue-spectrum laser scanners. Mesh is aligned against a CAD reference resulting in a colormap of deviations on the CAD surface	AR	Increased autonomy. Improved decision-making. Reduced scrap. BDA on data acquired. Added to Nvivo.	Augmented Operator, Smart Operator
Roberto, R. (2024a)	Off the Shelf AR Applications	(Unnamed)	Survey	Productivity	Industry's perception of deploying AR in manufacturing. Off-the-shelf and custom. AR to guide operators for adding external signs on aircraft. Detecting when operators are on wing to switch off non-essential functions and avoid distracting them, which could lead to a fall accident	AR	Added to Nvivo.	Augmented Operator
Roberto, R. (2024b)	Boeing Application	Boeing	Observations	Safety		AR, IoT	Increased safety. Improved decision making. Added to Nvivo.	Augmented Operator, Healthy Operator
Petzoldt, C. et al. (2020)	Informational Assistance Systems for Manual Assembly	(Unnamed)	Observations	Quality	Using IoT to improve manual assembly process. Use of screens, cameras and projector with gamification and ergonomic tracking	AR, IoT, BDA, AI	Improved ergonomics. Improved motivation. Improved performance. Increased autonomy. Added to Nvivo.	Smart Operator, Healthy Operator

11.15 Appendix O

Aerospace Focus Survey (Robinson, 2023)

11.16 Appendix P

O4.0 Bibliometric Analysis (Gladysz et al., 2023)